

Test and further develop a user-friendly Watershed Tool

By

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Abstract

The WOCAT Sustainable Land Management Watershed Tool (WT) allows to assess and illustrate the impacts of different land management practices on the “runoff” of small to medium-sized watersheds following a precipitation event. It is based on the Soil Conservation Service Curve Number methodology (SCS-CN). The method has only one parameter – the Curve Number (CN) – and is designed to be applied in ungauged watersheds. Based on several watershed characteristics (hydrologic soil group, land use and cover, hydrologic condition, structural measures, and slope) the representative CN can be estimated. Furthermore, it is possible to account for antecedent moisture conditions (AMC). AMC accounting is a three-staged process. AMC I represents dry, AMC II average, and AMC III wet conditions. The initial CN estimate is taken to be representative for AMC II. Suitable CNs for AMC I and AMC III are calculated based on the initial estimate.

The SCS-CN method can be applied in different forms. In the composite form a weighted CN is calculated for the whole watershed. In the distributed form, the “runoff” is calculated for smaller cells constituting the watershed.

In this thesis the opportunities and risks of the application of the WT are investigated and issues of its application are highlighted and discussed. A validity assessment of the WT is conducted through three case studies, whereby the SCS-CN method is applied in different forms – the composited, the distributed, and the calibrated form. Throughout the thesis, a special emphasis is placed on the application of the WT in different climatic settings and biomes. The first case study analyses three small, forested, very humid, and steep watersheds in the Orinoco river basin in Columbia. The second case study examines three small watersheds in the Ewaso Ng’iro close to the Mount Kenya, differing in terms of yearly precipitation, land cover and use, and slope. In the third case study the SCS-CN method is applied to 11 Swiss watersheds of different sizes.

Across all three studies the SCS-CN generally provided acceptable “runoff” estimates with average mean absolute errors of around 10mm for events above 50mm in the Switzerland and Columbia case study.

Through the case studies the following hypotheses about the SCS-CN method are investigated:

1. There is little to no relationship between the estimated CNs and the calibrated CNs for large sets of watersheds. (Hawkins, 1984)
2. The composited CN approach is generally less accurate than the distributed approach as it underestimates the representative CN. (Grove et al., 1998)
3. For each observed precipitation-“runoff” pair an ideal CN can be found. Event-wise ideal CNs tend to follow trends with changing precipitation, often decreasing with increasing precipitation until a near-constant value is approximated. This is called secondary P effect. (Hawkins, 1993)
4. It is claimed that AMC I and AMC III act as a surrogate for all other sources of variability. They approximate the bounds at the 90% and 10% exceedance frequency of event-wise ideal CNs in the near-constant CN range, respectively. (Hjelmfelt et al., 1981)

The case studies showed the following:

1. Not confirmed - for all examined watersheds (with the exception for one Swiss watershed) the representative CNs were correctly estimated. On average, the CN estimates differed by about 4.
2. Not confirmed - although the composited CN approach always leads to a lower “runoff” estimate, it is not possible to conclusively state that one approach is better. In the Swiss case

study, the distributed approach provided more accurate results for 4 of 11 watersheds. In the Columbian case study the composited CN performed better for all three watersheds.

3. Confirmed – in every analysed watershed a secondary P effect was identified . This emphasises that the WT should only be applied to large events.
4. Tentatively confirmed – in line with the hypothesis, in the Swiss case study, the CNs for AMC I and AMC III on average approximated the 88% and the 9% exceedance frequency. In the Columbian case study a similar tendency could be identified, however for a full assessment additional data is required.

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1. Introduction

The Sustainable Land Management Watershed Tool (WT) was developed in 2017 through a project of the World Overview of Conservation Approaches and Technologies (WOCAT) Network, an initiative of the Centre for Development and Environment (CDE) at the University of Bern. The tool allows to assess and showcase the impact of different land management practices on the “runoff” of small watersheds based on the *Soil Conservation Service Curve Number* methodology (SCS, 2004). (WOCAT, 2021)

The user-friendly set-up coupled with an easy and fast implementation of different land management scenarios are a key advantage of the tool. Furthermore, it is based on QGIS, a freely available software which makes it a low-cost option for communities (QGIS.org, 2021). In the past years the WT has been applied across a number of case studies in different biomes, climatic settings and of different scale. Unfortunately, none of these case studies provided the data necessary to validate the model (Joss, 2018) (Eichenberger, 2019) (Bandy, 2020). (Liniger et al., 2020)

The continued use of the WT across different settings with limited data availability calls for a comprehensive assessment of the applicability of the SCS-CN approach including the expected uncertainty in different settings (climate region, size, land use and cover, topography). This is particularly important as the application of the SCS-CN outside its designated scope (small agricultural watersheds in “humid” climate in the US¹) has led to criticism (Hawkins, 2009). Ogden et al. (2017) for example insisted that the hydrological community should acknowledge the SCS-CN method to serve “parsimonious niche applications” and to move “beyond the curve number” as a “one-size fits all” method.

In this thesis, the WT including the underlying SCS-CN methodology is studied. Its applicability and validity in different climatic settings is analysed theoretically and practically.

(i) Goal, Scope, and Structure

The goal of this thesis is threefold: to outline the opportunities and risks associated with the usage of the WOCAT SLM Watershed Tool, to improve the computational set-up of the WT (eliminating bugs, improved representation of results), and to give recommendations for its application.

Chapter 2 and 3 provide a comprehensive understanding of the WT and its recent applications including the underlying SCS-CN method. This is achieved through extensive literature review. The specific goals of the literature review are the following:

1. Present the state of the practice and often occurring misconceptions of the SCS-CN method.
2. Identify modifications and developments to the SCS-CN method for its application in ungauged watersheds.
3. Present the previous WT case studies.

In chapters 4 to 6 the Watershed Tool/SCS-CN method is applied to three case study regions in Columbia (3 watersheds), Kenya (3 watersheds), and Switzerland (11 watersheds). Specific goals of these case studies are the following:

1. Investigate and compare different forms of application of the SCS-CN methodology – calibrated vs. uncalibrated (based on tabulated values), distributed vs. composited, with accounting for antecedent moisture conditions vs. without accounting.
2. Determine and explain the validity of the “runoff” estimates obtained across different biomes and climatic settings.

¹ It is not entirely clear what datasets were used for determining the CN method. “It is known that most of the basic information was taken from small agricultural watersheds in humid settings, but without much basis in fact for deserts, forest, or urban watersheds. In addition, there is some indirect evidence that data from small river basins were also used.” (Hawkins, 2009, p. 61)

In chapter 7 the results of the literature review and the case studies are compared and identified issues are discussed. Recommendations and ideas to further develop the WT are presented.

Chapter 8 discusses practical computational issues of the WT and presents solutions and ideas to improve the model set-up.

In chapter 9 recommendations concerning future applications of the WT are presented.

(ii) The Term “Runoff”

In the original description of the SCS-CN method in the National Engineering Handbook, chapter 4 (NEH-4), the output of the SCS-CN method is called *direct runoff*. The term *direct runoff* refers to the volume water that is contributing to the streamflow at the outlet of a watershed as the consequence of a precipitation event. The water consists of channel runoff (precipitation falling on a flowing stream), surface runoff (water flowing on the surface of the watershed and through channels) and subsurface flow (infiltrated water that reappears as seep or spring) in unknown proportions. Baseflow (fairly steady flow from natural storage/aquifer) is excluded. (SCS, 2004)

Despite the clear definition in the NEH-4 the SCS-CN method is often thought of estimating only overland flow (unchanneled water flowing over the surface). Garen & Moore (2005) see the reason for this misconception in the diverging use of the word *runoff* in hydrological and engineering applications. Depending on the discipline and application, the term *runoff* can stand for streamflow or overland flow.

Although several authors have addressed this issue, the SCS-CN method is still often used for determining overland flow, interchangeably with the Green-Ampt infiltration model, which is conceptually erroneous (Garen & Moore, 2005). This issue is further discussed in section (xii).

In this thesis, several of the discussed studies using the SCS-CN method do not follow the process definition according to NEH-4. For these cases, the definitions given by the specific study will be applied and critically discussed. The WT itself uses the term *runoff*, analogue to the process overland flow (personal communication with Dr. Hanspeter Linger, 11.05.21).

2. Soil Conservation Service Curve Number

The SCS-CN was originally developed by the Natural Resources Conservation Service (formerly Soil Conservation Service) of the United States Department of Agriculture in 1954 based on extensive field-investigations in the U.S. in the 1930s and early 1940s. Since, the method has been revised several times. (SCS, 1956, 1964, 1971, 1972, 1985, 1993, 2004)

On the applicability of the SCS-CN methodology the NEH-4 states: “Curve numbers were originally developed from annual flood flows from experimental watersheds, and their application to low flows or small flood peak flows is not recommended.” (SCS, 2004, p. 10-19) In the light of the extensive use of the method outside the designated scope the following statement was added: “In the years following the development of the runoff equation, it has been adopted for use in applications that were not envisioned by the originator. Some of these applications are as an infiltration method for individual storm runoff events and as a loss function for continuous simulation. Such applications are not within the intended usage of curve number procedures.” (SCS, 2004, p. 10-19)

In the following the SCS-CN is presented and several important concepts, common issues and suggested improvements are critically discussed. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis is conducted.

(iii) Formulation

The SCS-CN method (SCS, 2004) is based on the water balance equation (1) and hypotheses (2) and (3):

$$P = I_a + F + Q \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{Q}{P - I_a} = \frac{F}{S} \quad (2)$$

$$I_a = \lambda S \quad (3)$$

where P [mm] is the total precipitation of an event, I_a [mm] is the initial abstraction (accounting for short term losses – interception, depression storage, infiltration before runoff commences, evapotranspiration, etc.), F [mm] is the cumulative infiltration excluding I_a , Q [mm] is the *direct runoff* (consists of channel runoff, surface runoff and subsurface flow in unknown proportions) and S [mm] is the potential maximum retention. Since the revision of the NEH-4 in 1959, it's assumed that $\lambda = 0.2$. With λ constant the SCS-CN is a 1-parameter model. (SCS, 2004)

The coupling (1) and (2) lead to equation (4):

$$Q = \frac{(P - I_a)^2}{P - I_a + S} \quad (4)$$

S can be determined from the Curve Number CN by using equation (5):

$$S = \frac{25400}{CN} - 254 \quad (5)$$

Figure 1 presents the output of the SCS-CN method. Q is shown for CNs between 30 and 100 and P between 0 and 140mm, when $\lambda = 0.2$. With increasing CNs and increasing P , Q is generally rising. However, for very low CNs and P s this tendency inverses. This limits the application scope of the SCS-CN method to watersheds with CN- P combinations on the right side of the inversion-line (where Q becomes 0mm). Below the inversion-line, the *direct runoff* is then set to 0mm. Thus,

$$\text{if } P - I_a < 0 \text{ then } Q = 0 \quad (6)$$

Figure 1. Variation of direct runoff (Q) with CNs between 30 and 100 and precipitation (P) between 0 and 140mm for a λ of 0.2.

The representative CN can either be obtained from calibration or read from tables such as in the NEH-4. The CN can be determined based on the following information: land use and cover, structural measure, hydrologic condition, and hydrologic soil group (SCS, 2004). Figure 2 depicts the workflow for applying the SCS-CN method by using tabulated values. Highlighted in light green are the input information needed for estimating the CN.

Figure 2. Workflow of SCS-CN method for the uncalibrated case.

Furthermore, it is possible to account for the influence of antecedent moisture condition (AMC) and slope by adapting the first estimate of the CN (highlighted in yellow; Note: slope accounting is further described in section (xi) as this is not part of the original form of the SCS-CN method.). In regard to the antecedent moisture conditions, one differentiates between AMC I (dry condition), AMC II (average condition) and AMC III (wet condition). The corresponding CNs are CN_I , CN_{II} and CN_{III} , respectively. The tabulated values represent CN_{II} . CN_I and CN_{III} can be calculated using the following equations:

$$CN_I = \frac{CN_{II}}{2.281 - 0.01281CN_{II}} \quad (7)$$

$$CN_{III} = \frac{CN_{II}}{0.427 + 0.00573CN_{II}} \quad (8)$$

From 1964 until the revision in 1993, the NEH-4 contained a guidance table on when to choose AMC I, II or III. The guidance was based on the 5-days antecedent precipitation and differentiated between dry and growing season. The table was removed from the NEH-4 in the wake of criticism concerning the lack of regional or scale differences (Ponce & Hawkins, 1996). Although the table is not included anymore in the NEH-4, the guidance table continues to be applied due to the lack of alternatives.

Table 1. Guidance for choosing antecedent moisture conditions. (from SCS (1964))

Moisture Condition (AMC)	Dry season	Growing Season
I	<12.7	< 35.6
II	12.7 – 27.9	35.6 – 53.3
III	> 27.9	> 53.3

(iv) *The Composite vs. Distributed CN Approach*

In practice, often one single CN is determined for the whole watershed. This can be done using the composite CN approach:

$$CN_w = \frac{CN_1A_1 + CN_2A_2 + \dots + CN_nA_n}{A} \quad (9)$$

where CN_w is the composited watershed curve number, CN_1, CN_2, \dots, CN_n are the curve numbers of the HRUs 1, 2, ..., n constituting the watershed, A [m^2] is the total watershed area, and A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n [m^2] are the areas of the HRUs 1, 2, ..., n constituting the watershed. (SCS, 2004) The composited *direct runoff* is then calculated via equations (4) and (5) by using CN_w .

Grove et al. (1998) states, that the composite CN approach “was originally developed as a time saving procedure, reducing the number of runoff calculations required.” (p.1015) Furthermore, it is criticised that compositing CNs is still common practice and used in many applications although there is no need for reduction of complexity anymore.

In the distributed CN approach, the *runoff* is calculated for smaller cells constituting the watershed. Hence the total watershed runoff can be calculated with the following equation:

$$Q_w = Q_1 + Q_2 + \dots + Q_n \quad (10)$$

where Q_w is the total watershed *runoff*, and Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_n are the *runoffs* from the HRUs 1, 2, ..., n constituting the watershed. (Grove et al., 1998)

Grove et al. (1998) investigated the difference in *runoff* of the two approaches for an idealized 100×100 cell matrix for multiple CN ranges and P s. The *runoff* was calculated for the composited and the distributed approach. Each grid cell was assigned a random CN from a uniform distribution in a specific range which was gradually increased. Additionally, the upper limit of the range was kept constant at a value of 98 and the lower limit was progressively decreased to 29. For the application of the composited approach the CNs were subsequently averaged. Figure 3 shows the resulting difference in *runoff* that was observed between the approaches for three different precipitation inputs. Grove et al. (1998) concluded the following:

- Significant errors in *runoff* estimates can occur when using composite CNs.
- The composite CN approach will always underestimate Q . This is a direct consequence of the exponential relationship with CN and Q .
- The difference between the two approaches gets bigger for lower P s, larger CN ranges, and lower CNs.

Figure 3. The effect of increasing CN on the percent increase in runoff depth calculated for distributed versus composite curve numbers for a range of precipitation values. (from Grove et al., 1998)

The NEH-4 recommends using the composite CN approach and does not mention the distributed approach. (SCS, 2004) This has some important implications:

- The CNs in the tables in the NEH-4 are based on the composite approach. One single CN was assumed for the whole watershed. They were not determined from watersheds with one single landuse and -cover, and soil type but were determined from heterogeneous watersheds with several different characteristics. The direct relationship between some watershed characteristics and a its *direct runoff* is hence not given. (see also section (xxxii)).
- In the following, several claims about the SCS-CN method are presented and critically investigated. All these claims are made based on the original form of the SCS-CN method that assumes a composite CN for the whole watershed and *direct runoff* as its output. This raises the question whether these claims are also relevant for the distributed approach (and the WT). This question is discussed in section (xxiv).

(v) Trends in Watershed Responses

When precipitation and *direct runoff* data are available, the optimal CN for a given P - Q -pair can be determined for each event. It has been observed that with changing precipitation these optimized CNs tend to follow specific trends. This phenomenon is called *secondary P effect* (Hawkins, 2009). Hawkins (1993) presents three typical trends of how watersheds are responding to changing precipitation inputs: complacent, standard, and violent behaviour. Examples for the three trends are shown in Figure 4, Figure 5, and Figure 6. The plots were created based on a frequency matching algorithm where the precipitation and runoff depths were sorted along size and rematched. When a watershed follows a complacent behaviour, the CN declines steadily with increasing P . This type of behaviour has primarily been detected for partial source area situations, where only around 0.1% – 5% of the area are responsible for most of the *direct runoff* (Hawkins, 1979). Standard behaviour is the most common behaviour. CNs decrease with a rising P until a near-constant value is approached. Violent behaviour is characterized by a sudden rise of CNs with rising P and asymptotic approach to a near-constant CN. A possible explanation for the violent behaviour might be a local storage that is withholding the water until a threshold is achieved.

Figure 4. Complacent behaviour of watershed response supported by data from West Donaldson Creek, Oregon (crosses). (from Hawkins, 1993)

Figure 5. Standard behaviour of watershed response (dashed line) supported by data from Coweeta watershed in North Carolina (crosses) and complacent behaviour West Donaldson Creek, Oregon (solid line). (from Hawkins, 1993)

Figure 6. Violent behaviour (dashed line) of watershed response supported by data from Berea watershed, Kentucky (crosses) and complacent behaviour West Donaldson Creek, Oregon (solid line). (from Hawkins, 1993)

Generally, the SCS-CN should only be applied to watersheds with standard or violent behaviour and for a precipitation range where a near constant CN is approached. To determine at which level of precipitation this is the case, Hawkins et al. (1985) proposed the following criterion:

$$S = 2.19P \quad (11)$$

This formula was derived based on considerations following the probability theory outlined in section (vi). At this threshold around 90% of all precipitation events create *direct runoff*.

The CNs that can be estimated from tables in the NEH-4 are chosen to approximate a representative CN for the near-constant CN range that is approached for high events.

(vi) Curve Number as a random Variable

The SCS-CN method explicitly considers the variability coming from antecedent moisture condition. However, other sources introducing variability in the precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour are not considered. These are:

- Distribution of precipitation over the duration of the storm
- Seasonal changes in the watershed condition (if the CN is not adapted throughout the year)
- Storm morphology
- Spatial and temporal variability of infiltration and other abstractive losses
- Arrangement and connectivity of different land uses and covers (LULC)²
- Quality of the measured data (only when calibrated)

A promising approach to the problem of variable watershed response is by defining the CN as a random variable. This allows to reflect the variability of Q for a certain watershed and for a given P as a distribution function. Furthermore, this variability can be modelled with the SCS-CN method by assuming the CN to follow its own distribution function (Hawkins, 1978) (Hjelmfelt et al., 1981) (McCuen, 2002).

² The model assumes that the surface runoff of each HRU is directly contributing to a channel. This is not necessarily the case.

Hjelmfelt et al. (1981) found that a log-normal probability distribution of CN approximates well the observed variability in watershed response. This conclusion was drawn from CNs based on annual maximum discharges from two small cropland watersheds. McCuen (2002) found that a two-parameter gamma distribution fits well the observed watershed response for 5 small agricultural watersheds in the rural area around Baltimore for annual maximum discharges.

Furthermore, Hjelmfelt et al. (1981) stated that CN_I and CN_{III} approximated the bounds at the 10th and 90th percentile of the empirically determined distribution function of CNs, respectively. Several investigations reinforcing this observation were presented by Haan & Schulze (1987) (six agricultural watersheds in the U.S. with around 30 years of record), Hauser & Jones (three agricultural field-scale watersheds with crop rotation in the southern Great Plains with 32 to 57 years of data), and Hjelmfelt (1991) (14 U.S. watersheds incl. forested, agricultural, and urban with 8 to 24 years of data) (see Figure 7). McCuen (2002) found that the Q obtained for CN_I and CN_{III} were wider than the 1% confidence bounds of the distribution function of Q .

These considerations indicate that the concept of antecedent soil moisture is a surrogate for all other sources of variability mentioned (Ponce & Hawkins, 1996).

Figure 7. Comparison of CNs for 10% and 90% exceedance frequency with those for AMC I and AMC III for 14 watersheds in the U.S. (from Hjelmfelt, 1991)

For such an approach of the SCS-CN method to work, it is essential that only large enough events are used (i.e. in the range of precipitation intensity where we approach one single near-constant CN). Smaller events would likely introduce a bias due to the secondary P effect.

Soulis & Valiantzas (2012) critically investigated the concept of CN as a random variable. It was stated that in this analysis it was neglected to include that "...CN values calculated from measured precipitation-

runoff data vary systematically with the precipitation depth.” (p. 1001) This will further be discussed in section (xxxi).

(vii) Sensitivity Analysis

In the following sub-chapter the absolute sensitivity of the SCS-CN method to the CN and P is evaluated. λ is assumed to take a value of 0.2. The sensitivity analysis was conducted for CNs between 30 and 100 and P between 0 and 140mm. Hereby, Q was calculated for all combinations of CNs and P s rising in steps of 0.5 and 0.5mm, respectively. The absolute sensitivity of a given P -CN-combination was calculated with the following formula:

$$S_{i,j}^{CN} = \frac{Q_{i-1,j} + Q_{i+1,j}}{CN_{i-1,j} + CN_{i+1,j}} \tag{12}$$

$$S_{i,j}^P = \frac{Q_{i,j-1} + Q_{i,j+1}}{P_{i,j-1} + P_{i,j+1}} \tag{13}$$

i is the index of the CN rising in steps of 0.5, j is the index of the P rising in steps of 0.5mm, $S_{i,j}^{CN}$ is the absolute sensitivity of $Q_{i,j}$ to the CN, $S_{i,j}^P$ is the absolute sensitivity of $Q_{i,j}$ to P .

Figure 7 and 8 show the absolute sensitivity of Q to P and of Q to CN, respectively. On the right side of the inversion line (see section (iii)), the sensitivity of Q to P and CN is rising with increasing CN and increasing P . The relative sensitivity of Q to CN is decreasing with rising CNs and rising P (see Appendix, Figure 45 and equation (42)).

Figure 8. Absolute sensitivity of direct runoff (Q) to precipitation (P) for CNs between 30 and 100, P between 0 and 140mm for a λ of 0.2

Figure 9. Absolute sensitivity of direct runoff (Q) to CN for CNs between 30 and 100, precipitation (P) between 0 and 140mm for a λ of 0.2.

(viii) Critique

Since its development the SCS-CN method has been subject of intense discussions among experts. In the following several pros and cons of the SCS-CN method are described. Ponce & Hawkins (1996) summarize the advantages and limitations of the SCS-CN method as:

- Perceived advantages are: Its simplicity, its predictability, its stability, its reliance on only one parameter and its responsiveness to major runoff-producing watershed properties.
- Perceived limitations are:
 - (1) The marked sensitivity to curve number
 - (2) The absence of clear guidance on how to vary antecedent condition
 - (3) The method's varying accuracy of different biomes
 - (4) The absence of an explicit provision for spatial scale effects
 - (5) The fixing of the initial abstraction ratio at 0.2

Other perceived limitations of the SCS-CN method are:

- (6) S The assumption of a linear $I_a - S$ relation (Plummer & Woodward, 2002)
- (7) The three-staged structure of accounting for AMC (Mishra et al., 2002)

In the following these limitations are further described:

(1) The marked sensitivity to curve number - Under low CNs and low precipitation depths, the *direct runoff* is very sensitive to the CN. For modelling purposes this may seem like a weak point, but it is also a reflection of the underlying natural variability. This means that there is a large variability occurring for small precipitation events. The large sensitivity of the model in low CN and precipitation range is a consequence. (Ponce & Hawkins, 1996)

(2) The absence of clear guidance on how to vary antecedent condition - With the removal of Table 1 from the NEH-4, there is no guidance of when to choose AMC I, II or III. This lack of guidance might lead to errors in the application of the SCS-CN method when uncalibrated. A typical error is to assume that in a location with very dry climate one should always select CN_I . However, according to Hawkins et al. (2009), for any site and soil cover status CN_{II} should always be selected as the local reference point, regardless of climate. (Ponce & Hawkins, 1996)

(3) The method's varying accuracy of different biomes - The SCS-CN was designed to reproduce the behaviour of small to medium sized, humid agricultural watersheds in the U.S. Practice confirmed that the method performs best for agricultural watersheds. Also, for urban watersheds good results are obtained. However, for range sites and for forested watersheds poor performance should be expected. (Ponce & Hawkins, 1996)

(4) The absence of an explicit provision for spatial scale effects - With increasing watershed size channel transmission losses – evaporation from free water surfaces and infiltration into channel beds, banks, and flood plains (Smakhtin & Watkins, 2017) – are generally increasing. This problem can be obviated by subdivision of the watershed combined with channel routing. (Ponce & Hawkins, 1996)

(5) The fixing of the initial abstraction ratio at 0.2 - The original form of the SCS-CN method assumed λ to be 0.2. However, using λ as a parameter could “enhance the method's responsiveness to a diversity of geologic and climatic settings” (Ponce & Hawkins, 1996, p.17).

(6) S The assumption of a linear $I_a - S$ relation - The first version of the of the SCS-CN method did not yet include λ (SCS, 1956). Only in the year 1959 equation (3) with $\lambda = 0.2$ was added (SCS, 1959). For the same land use and conditions several different CNs were presented for the two cases. There is however no linear relationship between the CNs as it is suggested today. In theory each relationship of I_a and S requires a unique catalogue of CNs. To assume a linear relationship between I_a and S is an oversimplification. (Plummer and Woodward, 2002)

(7) The three-staged structure of accounting for AMC - Antecedent moisture conditions can only be accounted for in stages – dry, average, wet. In practical applications sudden jumps in CN and *direct runoff* appear when changing from one level to another.

(ix) *CNs estimated from P-Q Data*

When the watershed follows a standard or violent behaviour (see section 0), a calibration can be performed that determines the asymptotic CN for high precipitation inputs. This can be achieved by using observed P - Q -pairs. CN can be found by applying the *storm event method* which is using the following equation developed by Hawkins (1973).

When $\lambda = 0.2$:

$$S = 5 \left(P + 2Q - \sqrt{4Q^2 + 5PQ} \right) \quad (14)$$

In the general case, when $\lambda \neq 0.2$ equation (43) in the Appendix can be used.

Again, the calibration should only be applied to each observed precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs above the threshold for asymptotic behaviour. From the obtained set of S the mean or median is taken as the S representing the watershed behaviour.

Other well-known approaches with the same purpose are the asymptotic (*rank order*) approach described by Hjelmfelt (1980) and the *frequency method* by Schneider & McCuen (2005).

If the watershed follows complacent behaviour, the SCS-CN method should not be applied. No CN can be found that would be able to reproduce the behaviour of the watershed over a range of P s. In this case, the precipitation-direct runoff relationship can better be modelled using a linear formulation. (Hawkins, 1993)

(x) *The uncalibrated Case*

In the case that no or insufficient data is available the NEH-4 provides tables from which the CNs can be determined. The accuracy of the estimates based on these tables has been analysed in several studies. Hawkins (1984) compared the tabulated CNs with the CNs obtained from P - Q -pairs for 110 watersheds in the U.S. It was concluded that there was “only a faint suggestion of trend, and thus of any reasonable association between predicted and observed curve numbers.” (Hawkins, 1984, p. 705) Other studies made similar observations. Titmarsh et al. (1995) compared the CNs obtained from tables and from measured precipitation-runoff data of 105 watersheds in Australia and concluded that “...the conventional handbook values will give inaccurate estimates of design runoff and flood peaks.” (Titmarsh et al., 1995, p. 69) (see Figure 10) D’Asaro et al. (2014) compared the CNs of 36 watersheds in Sicily, Italy and concluded: “On average, estimates of CN from the Handbook tables do not compare well with the data-based estimates, and correlation was not significant between them.” (p. 11)

Figure 10. Comparison of CN values obtained from NEH-4 tables and from rainfall-runoff data for 105 watersheds in Southeast Queensland, Australia. (from Titmarsh et al., 1995)

In a further analysis of predicted versus observed CNs, Hawkins et al. (1984) segregated the land cover types into agriculture, range, and forest. A significant difference could be found between the three land cover types in terms of accuracy of estimates. The estimates for the agricultural watersheds were considered most accurate followed by the range sites and finally the forested watersheds. Hawkins (1984, p.706) added: “This should not be surprising, since the methodology and table estimates of CN were originally established for agricultural lands.”

(xi) Modifications

The SCS-CN method has been modified by numerous authors. Many modifications are applied to the original form of the SCS-CN method but introduce a new way to handle one or more limitations stated in section (viii). Generally, the modifications of the SCS-CN try to improve the original SCS-CN method by:

- a. Model adaptation: Model redefinition by keeping one single parameter. The following modifications are common practice:
 - i. Conceptual Redefinition of AMC
 - ii. $\lambda \neq 0.2$

- b. Alternations of CN estimation: Change the values of the estimation tables or add watershed characteristics for determining the representative CN. Typical alternations concerning the determination of representative CNs (b) are the following:
 - iii. Numerical Redefinition of AMC
 - iv. Accounting for Slope

- c. Model extension: Model redefinition that introduces new parameters into the model. Often additional parameters account for another source of variability affecting the precipitation-*direct runoff* relationship (e.g. spatio-temporal variability of precipitation).

Most of the modifications are model extensions, but as such extensions generally increase the complexity and are therefore less relevant for ungauged watersheds. For this reason, these modifications are not further described.

In the following, well established modifications of the SCS-CN concerning categories (i) – (iv) are presented:

(i) Conceptual Redefinition of AMC - Mishra & Singh (2002b) reconsidered the concept of antecedent soil moisture and came up with the following equation for estimating the direct runoff:

$$Q = \frac{(P - I_a)(P - I_a + M)}{P - I_a + M + S} \quad (15)$$

where in the case of $\lambda = 0.2$:

$$M = 0.5 \left(-1.2S + \sqrt{0.64S^2 + 4P_5S} \right) \quad (16)$$

Here, P_5 is the amount of 5-day antecedent precipitation and M is the estimated antecedent soil moisture. In the general case, when $\lambda \neq 0.2$ equation (44) in the Appendix can be used.

With the reconsideration of the antecedent soil moisture two issues are tackled: First, it proposes a clear guidance on how to vary antecedent soil moisture. Second, it obviates the three-stage structure of the old AMC concept that leads to sudden jumps of CN values.

Within SWAT, the concept of AMC is rethought and directly connected to the amount of soil water which makes it also possible to obviate sudden jumps of the CN (see Appendix, *Surface Runoff Component of the Soil & Water Assessment Tool*).

(ii) $\lambda \neq 0.2$ - Many studies have probed the formulation $\lambda = 0.2$ (Cazier & Hawkins, 1984) (Jiang, 2001) (Hawkins & Khojeini, 2000). Often different values for λ were found. Generally, the studies find that $\lambda = 0.05$ is often a good choice (Hawkins et al., 2009). As the NEH-4 assumes $\lambda = 0.2$ an adaptation of the tabulated values would be required when another λ is used.

The CN is of higher importance than the λ . According to Schneider & McCuen (2005) λ is a relatively insensitive parameter and study-to-study differences are to be expected. However, large variations of λ such as the shift to $\lambda = 0.05$ as proposed by Hawkins et al. (2009) would lead to significant change in the resulting *direct runoff*.

Figure 11 shows the absolute sensitivity of *direct runoff* for a decrease of λ by 0.003 for a P between 0 and 140mm and a CN of 70. The sensitivity analysis is computed in the same manner as in section (vii). With decreasing λ , the direct runoff is rising. For a decrease of from $\lambda = 0.2$ to $\lambda = 0.05$ and a precipitation input of 60mm a rise of the *direct runoff* of around 8mm occurs. With rising P and rising CN the absolute sensitivity to λ is rising. Again, for the range in which $\frac{\Delta Q}{\Delta 0.003\lambda} < 0$ the SCS-CN method is not applicable and Q is set to 0.

Figure 11. Absolute sensitivity of direct runoff (Q) to a decrease of λ by 0.003 for precipitation (P) between 0 and 140mm, λ between 0 and 0.3, and for a CN of 70.

(iii) Numerical Redefinition of AMC - Many authors have proposed different equations for determining the CNs for AMCs based on the old three-staged concept. For example, equations (17) and (18) were created during the development of the hydrological model called Soil & Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) (Nietsch et al., 2009).

$$CN_I = CN_{II} - \frac{2000 - 20CN_{II}}{(100 - CN_{II} + e^{2.533-6.36-0.0636CN_{II}})} \quad (17)$$

$$CN_{III} = CN_{II} \cdot e^{0.673-0.00673CN_{II}} \quad (18)$$

Other possible ways for calculating AMC are given by Chow et al. (1988) and Mishra et al. (2008).

(iv) Accounting for Slope - Sharpley & Williams (1990) stated, that the CN_{II} values in the NEH-4 tables fitted best for slopes of around 5% and proposed the following formula to account for slope-correction:

$$CN_{II\alpha} = \frac{1}{3}(CN_{III} - CN_{II})(1 - 2e^{-13.86\alpha}) + CN_{II} \quad (19)$$

where CN_{II} is the Curve Number for AMC III calculated with equation (18), and $CN_{II\alpha}$ is the slope-corrected CN_{II} and α is the slope.

Other slope adjustments were presented by Williams & Izaurrealde (2005), Huang et al. (2006), and Ajmal et al. (2016).

(xii) Erroneous Uses

The SCS-CN method is widely accepted for its designated application: Precipitation-runoff modelling for large storm events in medium-sized agricultural watersheds in the U.S. However, its extensive use outside this narrow scope of application has been criticized. Garen & Moore (2005) detect two different types of frequent misapplications:

1. The method is often implemented in models for estimating erosion and water quality. For such applications, the SCS-CN method is used as a point-scale infiltration equation, i.e. Q is the non-infiltrating precipitation. This is an erroneous use, as the method is not used for what it was designed for – estimating *direct runoff* on the watershed scale. Garen & Moore (2005) explain the error comes from a misunderstanding of the definition of the term *runoff* (see also section (i)). When the SCS-CN method is wrongly assumed to exclusively compute overland flow, this has the following implications:
 - The only process responsible for producing overland flow is infiltration excess runoff and it is assumed to occur over the entire surface area. All other processes contributing to the *direct runoff* – namely saturation excess overland flow, channel runoff, subsurface flow – are neglected.
 - It becomes possible by mistake to apply the method to any spatial scale – point, plot, field, or watershed.
2. The SCS-CN methodology is often used to compute continuous time series of *direct runoff* and soil moisture. Following Garen & Moore (2005), this use is an incorrect application because the SCS-CN usually only approximates a constant value for large events (see section 0). The watershed response for small and large precipitation events is not optimally modelled by the same CN due to the secondary P effect. This will lead to errors. At what event-size these errors occur depends on the chosen CN and the precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour of the modelled watershed.

Several, well known hydrological models such as SWAT or the Hydrologic Modelling System (HEC-HMS) use the SCS-CN method in a continuous manner and interpret the Q as overland flow (Nietsch et al., 2009)

(Feldman, 2000). Following the rationale of Garen & Moore (2005), these models are therefore using the method in the conceptually erroneous way. Still, SWAT and HEC-HMS are said to be able to accurately reproduce precipitation-streamflow relationships with this surface runoff component.

The authors of the SWAT model state on the applicability of the SCS-CN method: “SWAT is a continuous model, i.e. a long-term yield model. The model is not designed to simulate detailed, single-event flood routing.” (Nietsch et al., 2009, p.2) This statement is in direct opposition to the comments in the NEH-4: “Curve numbers were originally developed from annual flood flows from experimental watersheds, and their application to low flows or small flood peak flows is not recommended.” (SCS, 2004, p. 10-19)

How it is possible that well established models use the CN-method in a wrong way and are accepted as accurate will be discussed further in section (xxx) with the example of SWAT.

A detailed description of the surface runoff component in the SWAT model is presented in the Appendix, Surface Runoff Component of the Soil & Water Assessment Tool.

3. The WOCAT SLM Watershed Tool

The mode of operation of the WT is described in the *User Manual for the WOCAT SLM Watershed Tool* (Liniger, 2020). The WT allows the user to delineate watersheds based on Google Maps satellite imagery in QGIS. A watershed can further be split up into different HRUs. Every HRU needs manual inputs of land use type, specific cropland measures, hydrologic condition of the soil, slope, and the daily precipitation. Based on this information, the *runoff* of each HRU is calculated using the original Soil Conservation Service Curve Number (SCS-CN) methodology with $\lambda = 0.2$. The total *runoff* of the watershed is calculated as the sum of all HRUs. Furthermore, the WT accounts for the slope with the equation (19) developed by Sharpley & Williams (1990). There is no accounting for antecedent soil moisture included in the WT. However, the slope accounting requires CN_i and CN_{iii} , which are calculated with equations (17) and (18), respectively. (Liniger et al., 2020)

Based on the output of the WT a water balance approach was developed. It has been applied in three different case studies so far – the Cormier watershed in Haiti and the Vaishnavi and Shivalaya watersheds in Uttarakhand, India. The mode of operation of the water balance approach will be described further in the Case Study 3: Two small spring sheds in Uttarakhand, India – Bandy (2020).

(xiii) Case Studies

In the following, the three case studies which are part of the ongoing research on the WT are presented. The studies are briefly summarized, with a focus on the technical details around the application of the WT or the SCS-CN in general. The three studies will be critically reviewed as part of this thesis theoretical analysis.

(xiv) Case Study 1: Three large Watersheds in Kenya – Joss (2018)

Joss (2018) intended to apply the WT to assess the impact of LULC on the *runoff* in the lower Ewaso Ng'iro basin. However, due to the size of the investigated watersheds and the use of very high resolution, QGIS did not perform in a stable manner. Faster and more stable data processing could be achieved by implementing the SCS-CN method using the software R and adopting the same methodology as in the WT. Three large watersheds with a size of 9'000, 1'400 and 800 km² were investigated. The watersheds extended over various climatic zones – from humid mountain zones to arid and semi-arid areas. An automated pixel-based classification algorithm using Google Earth Engine imagery was created to divide the area into different LULC zones. Based on the newly created LULC map, a soil map and slope, HRUs were defined. A D8 flow algorithm was used to determine the channel network. HRUs were only allowed to extend over an area contributing to one single channel. For each HRU the *runoff* was determined for any given scenario. 10 different scenarios were considered – specifically any combination of five

precipitation intensities 11mm, 21mm, 49mm, 69mm, and 107mm and two LULC maps (for wet and dry period). The precipitation intensities were chosen based on weather products obtained from satellites, namely the Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) product provided by the *National Centre for Environmental Prediction*. As no precipitation data from gauging stations inside the investigated area were available, no reasonable validity assessment of the obtained precipitation-*runoff* relationship could be conducted. However, reasonable streamflow data were available at the outlet for two of the three watersheds. The measured total daily *runoff* volume for several big storms in both watersheds would have been correctly simulated for storm events between 21mm (monthly maximum 0.5 quantile estimated from CFSR) and 49mm (annual maximum 0.5 quantile estimated from CFSR). As big storms are expected to be in this range – these measurements are indicating that the modelled *runoff* has approximately the right magnitude. (Joss, 2018)

(xv) Case Study 2: Cormier Watershed in Haiti – Eichenberger (2019)

The Cormier watershed covers an area of around 30km² and is primarily used for small scale farming purposes. It has tropic climate in in dry winter (November – March) and two pronounced rainy seasons (April – May, August – October). Eichenberger (2019) used the WT to explore land management practices for decreasing flood risk. Six different LULC scenario maps were defined, and the *runoff* was simulated and analysed for each of them. The LULC maps were determined and adapted from WorldView-2 satellite imagery and object-based image analysis. The following scenarios were considered: dry, average, wet soil moisture condition (LULC_{dry}, LULC_{avg}, LULC_{wet}), poor practice (LULC_{poor}), vetiver terrasses (LULC_{vetiver}), and agroforestry systems (LULC_{AF}). LULC_{dry} and LULC_{wet} were calculated using the methodology for accounting for antecedent moisture conditions given by equations (17) and (18). The assessment of bad and good land use practices (LULC_{poor}, LULC_{vetiver}, LULC_{AF}) was conducted for average antecedent soil moisture conditions. As there were no streamflow data available, it was not possible to reasonably validate the simulated *runoff*. Consequently, it was stated: “Therefore, this thesis can only make meaningful statements about the potential surface runoff contribution of different land uses and based on this identify potential hotspot areas.” (Eichenberger, 2019, pp. 9) (Eichenberger, 2019)

(xvi) Case Study 3: Two small spring sheds in Uttarakhand, India – Bandy (2020)

Bandy (2020) applied the WT to two spring sheds in the region of Uttarakhand, India – the Vaishnavi and the Shivalaya spring shed. They occupy an area of 15.5 ha and 3.7 ha, respectively. The WT was used to determine the daily *runoff*. Based on the obtained daily *runoff* and estimations of the daily actual evapotranspiration (ET_a), the spring recharge was modelled. The used methodology is called water balance approach and is implemented in Microsoft Excel. (Bandy, 2020)

The conceptual two-reservoir framework of the water balance approach is shown in Figure 12. SW(t) is the amount of soil water at a certain time t. The volume of the soil water storage reservoir (SS) defines the maximum amount of water, the soil can hold. It is fed by incoming infiltration. Infiltrated water can either leave the SS as evaporation or as groundwater recharge. The method was applied on a daily temporal scale. The approach estimates the recharge of the groundwater reservoir (GW) based on the following assumptions:

- The daily infiltration is estimated from the following water balance:

$$F = P - Q \tag{20}$$

where F is the daily infiltration into the SS, P is the daily precipitation and Q is the *runoff* estimated from the WT.

- Groundwater is only recharged when the SS is completely filled – SW(t) exceeds SS on a given day. All surplus water exceeding the SS will be allocated to the GW.

Daily evaporation rate and a convenient SS are needed. They can be obtained from literature data, field observation or expert knowledge. The *PET* was estimated on a monthly basis for different LULCs complexes from previous research projects in the Uttarakhand region. (Bandy, 2020)

Figure 12. Conceptual framework of water balance approach.

In both applications the water balance approach was applied to each WT HRU individually. The daily evaporation rate as well as the SS were varied for different HRUs. (Bandy, 2020) (Liniger & Bandy, 2020)

4. Case Study Region – Columbia

The WT was applied to three neighbouring watersheds located in the northern eastern Andes of Columbia that were intensely examined in the work of Ramírez et al. (2017, 2018). The investigated area is particularly interesting as the watersheds are covered by tropical montane cloud forests, which are characterized by a persistent fog. Generally, the area is very wet. Over the measurement period (353 days) around 4000mm precipitation was observed. A dry season occurred between December and March and a wet season between April and November. (Ramírez et al., 2017 and 2018)

For the time between 12.06.2014 (day 1) and 30.05.2015 (day 353) streamflow data at the outlet and watershed averaged precipitation inputs are available (prepared by Dr. Beatriz Ramírez). The precipitation averaging was conducted using the inverse distance and elevation weighting interpolation method following Masih et al. (2011) making use of daily precipitation data from 5 gauges. The watersheds are covered by grassland and tropical forests in unequal proportions. In this study the three watersheds will be referred to as deforested, intermediately forested and forested as shown in Figure 13. Ramírez (2018) differentiated between four different land uses – old-growth forest, secondary forest, early forest, and grazing land. This classification was adopted for the application of the WT as shown in Table 2. The watersheds are steep with average slopes of 18% to 26%. (Ramírez et al., 2017 and 2018)

Several characteristics of the watersheds are shown in Table 3. Further description of the study area can be found in Ramírez et al. (2017) and Ramírez et al. (2018).

Figure 13. The three investigated watersheds close to Chámeza, Columbia, and the HURs with their corresponding land uses (see Table 2) and the location of the rain gauges (indicated with the red diamonds). From left to right: deforested, intermediately forested, forested.

Table 2. Classification of land use along Ramirez et al. (2018) and classification applied in the Watershed Tool with corresponding CN without accounting for slope.

Color	Classification along Ramirez et al. (2018)	WT: Land Use	WT: Hydrologic Condition	CN without accounting for slope
	Old-growth forest	Fn: Natural	good	60
	Secondary forest	Fn: Natural	fair	69
	Early forest	Fn: Natural	poor	80
	Grazing land	Ge: Extensive grazing land	fair	80

*information from personal communication with Beatriz Ramirez, 31.03.2021

Table 3. Elevation range, size, average slope, total measured precipitation (353 days), and percentage of land covered forest and grassland for the three investigated watersheds close to Chámeza, Columbia.

Watershed	Elev. Range [m.a.s.l.]	Size [km ²]	Average Slope [m/m]	Total measured precipitation [mm]	Forest / Grassland
Deforested	1575-2241	3.71	18	3869	71% / 29%
Intermediately Forested	1550-2256	3.50	17	3876	84% / 16%
Forested	1668-2490	3.02	26	4648	99% / 1%

A baseflow separation was conducted following the approach described by the Institute of Hydrology (1980) in the same form as applied by Tallaksen & van Lanen (2004). The baseflow for each day was calculated by linear interpolation between the daily streamflow minima of non-overlapping, consecutive 5-day intervals. If the calculated baseflow exceeded the streamflow, the daily baseflow was reduced to the level of the streamflow.

Figure 14, Figure 15, and Figure 16 show the measured streamflow, the measured precipitation, and the calculated baseflow contribution for the three watersheds. The corresponding *direct runoff* (on a daily basis) was calculated with the following equation:

$$Q = \text{Streamflow} - \text{Baseflow} \quad (21)$$

The obtained *direct runoff* will be defined as “measured *direct runoff*”.

It can be observed that the deforested watershed generated higher streamflow peaks than the intermediately forested and the forested watershed although the precipitation input was similar in all watersheds. This is a clear indication for a change in the precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour with changing land cover.

Figure 14. Precipitation, streamflow measurements and baseflow contribution for the deforested watershed close to Chámeza, Columbia.

- Streamflow Measurements
- Calculated Baseflow Contribution
- Precipitation Measurements

Figure 15. Precipitation, streamflow measurements and baseflow contribution for the intermediately forested watershed close to Chámeza, Columbia.

— Streamflow Measurements
 — Calculated Baseflow Contribution
 — Precipitation Measurements

Figure 16. Precipitation, streamflow measurements and baseflow contribution for the forested watershed close to Chámeza, Columbia.

— Streamflow Measurements
 — Calculated Baseflow Contribution
 — Precipitation Measurements

For the application of the WT the land use polygons of Ramirez et al. (2018) were used. For the whole area a soil type of C was assumed. This assumption is based on the global soil maps prepared by Ross et al. (2018). The mean slope [m/m] of each HRU was calculated based on the 30m×30m DEM product from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) (NASA JPL, 2013). For the deforested and intermediately forested case, Q was estimated with the WT for different P inputs. Based on the modelled direct runoffs, a trendline was created using a 2nd order polynomial. The following polynomials were found for the deforested watershed:

$$Q = 0.004P^2 + 0.0093P - 1.1067 \text{ for } CN_{II} \quad (22)$$

$$Q = 0.0027P^2 - 0.1765P + 2.9448 \text{ for } CN_I \quad (23)$$

$$Q = 0.004P^2 + 0.0093P - 1.1067 \text{ for } CN_{III} \quad (24)$$

and for the intermediately forested watershed:

$$Q = 0.0041P^2 - 0.0531P - 0.4411 \text{ for } CN_{II} \quad (25)$$

$$Q = 0.0021P^2 - 0.1448P + 2.5861 \text{ for } CN_I \quad (26)$$

$$Q = 0.0039P^2 + 0.3427P - 0.29977 \text{ for } CN_{III} \quad (27)$$

As the forested watershed only had one land use type, the precipitation-*direct runoff* relationship was calculated directly from the CNs obtained from the WT which had values of 65.8 (CN_{II}), 45.8 (CN_I), and 86.1 (CN_{III}).

In the Figure 17, Figure 18, and Figure 19 the precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs deduced from measurements and estimated from the WT as well as the trendline for the estimations are shown. The figures have the following legend:

- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{II}
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_I
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{III}
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_{II}
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_I
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_{III}
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{II}
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_I
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{III}

Figure 17. Measured and simulated precipitation-direct runoff pairs and trendlines for the simulated pairs for CN_{II} (average), CN_I (dry), and CN_{III} (wet) for the deforested watershed close to Chámeza, Columbia.

Figure 18. Measured and simulated precipitation-direct runoff pairs and trendlines for the simulated pairs for CN_{II} (average), CN_I (dry), and CN_{III} (wet) for the intermediately forested watershed close to Chámeza, Columbia.

Figure 19. Measured and simulated precipitation-direct runoff pairs and the curves following the SCS-CN method for a CN of 65.8 (CN_{II}, average), 45.8 (CN_I, dry), and 86.1 (CN_{III}, wet) for the forested watershed close to Chámeza, Colombia.

No clear trend can be observed between the observed P - Q -pairs and the assigned AMC. For large events the precipitation-*direct runoff* relationship is well modelled without accounting for antecedent moisture conditions. Smaller events are generally underestimated. These observations are in line with the theory concerning the secondary P effect presented in section 0. The occurrence of a secondary P effect is also indicated in the plots depicting the ideal CNs for the sorted observed precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs (see Digital Appendix, Columbia\Watershed Response).

It can further be observed that the watershed response in the deforested watershed had a larger variability than in the intermediately forested and the forested watershed. One explanation for this behaviour might be small scale intensity differences in precipitation. Intense precipitation onto the deforested area is likely to cause high *direct runoffs*. However, if a large part of the precipitation is falling on the forested part of the watershed the direct runoff is likely to be lower. Heterogeneous high intensity precipitation is typical for the region (personal communication with Hanspeter Liniger, 01.09.2021). Another explanation might be the variability of vegetation growth throughout the year in the deforested area.

Several events could be observed that had a higher *direct runoff* than precipitation input for some days. This is in principle impossible. All these events occurred for low precipitation inputs below 15mm. A prominent example is the precipitation-*direct runoff* pair recorded on the 16.07.2014 in the intermediately forested watershed. This event has a precipitation input of 10mm but a *direct runoff* of 30mm (with a streamflow of 48mm). Three possible causes for these events are the following:

- Errors in the precipitation or streamflow measurement.
- The SCS-CN method is designed to be an event-based method. If it is applied on daily measurements it happens that events are split up in their allocation. Hereby the temporal shift

between the precipitation falling on the watershed and the direct runoff leaving the watershed can lead to errors.

- The Institute of Hydrology (1980) approach is a simplistic approach that assumes the baseflow based on the consecutive non-overlapping 5 days minima. For small events, even small deviances from the actual baseflow lead to large differences in what is accounted as *direct runoff*.

For all case studies these three sources of uncertainty have to be always considered to have a significant influence on the validity assessment (see also section (xxxiii), (xxxiii), and (xxxiii)).

For the event on the 16.07.2014 the following watershed response could be observed:

Figure 20. Precipitation, streamflow measurements and baseflow contribution for the days 27 to 36 (09.07.2014 to 18.07.2014) for the intermediately forested watershed close to Chámeza, Columbia.

— Streamflow Measurements
 — Calculated Baseflow Contribution
 — Precipitation Measurements

The 5-days antecedent precipitation before the 16.07.2014 was 200mm. On the 15.07.2014 the streamflow began to rise intensely. The high streamflow continued until the 17.07.2014. These observations suggest that the streamflow on the 16.07.2014 was mainly fed by precipitation water that fell the days before. In the deforested watershed a similar precipitation input could be observed (see Figure 21). However in contrast to the intermediately forested watershed the streamflow increased rapidly and stayed above 40mm between 12.07.2014 and 18.07.2014. In the forested watershed the peak streamflow was achieved already on the 15.07.2014 and decreased down to 30mm on the 16.07.2014 (see Digital Appendix, Columbia\Data_Calcualtions). Although the deforested showed a similar streamflow of 46mm for a precipitation input of 20mm on the 16.07.2014, the *direct runoff* was significantly lower than for the intermediately forested watershed. The crucial difference however is that in the deforested watershed, the baseflow contribution was higher with 36mm compared to 18mm in the intermediately forested watershed. These considerations are indicating that the baseflow was underestimated in the case of the intermediately forested watershed. This is a consequence of Institute of Hydrology approach applied. Especially questionable is also the unusual precipitation-streamflow

behaviour on the 14.07.2014. On this day the streamflow decreased although 54mm of precipitation were falling.

Figure 21. Precipitation, streamflow measurements and baseflow contribution for the days 27 to 36 (09.07.2014 to 18.07.2014) for the intermediately forested watershed close to Chámeza, Columbia.

The equations (22) and (25), representing the trendlines for CN_{II} for the deforested and intermediately forested watershed, and the SCS-CN method using CN_{II} 65.8 of the forested watershed were applied on each day using the corresponding measured precipitation input of each watershed. In this way, the estimated *direct runoff* for each day was determined without accounting for antecedent moisture conditions.

The same analysis was repeated by accounting for antecedent moisture condition. The AMC of each day was determined using Table 1. Hereby, the time from December and March was counted as *Dry Season* and the time from April to November was accounted as *Wet Season*. Then, the corresponding equation was used to determine the daily *direct runoff* – equation (22), (23), or (24) for the deforested, equation (25), (26), or (27) for the intermediately forested and the SCS-CN method with 65.8 (CN_{II}), 45.8 (CN_I), or 86.1 (CN_{III}) for the forested watershed.

To check the accuracy of the CN estimations the mean absolute error (MAE) was determined for the composited, the distributed, and the calibrated CN approach. Only events above 50mm precipitation were considered. This threshold was chosen as a trade-off between the need for enough data points and the criterion given by equation (11) which is often not met with this threshold. Still, as the secondary P effect is generally increasing for lower precipitation inputs, the slight undercutting of the criterion is

assumed to cause only minor deviances. The calculations can be found in the Digital Appendix, Columbia\Columbia_Data_Calcualtions.

The calibrated CNs were found with the *storm event method* (see equation (14)). The median of the event-wise optimized CNs for all precipitation events above 50mm was chosen as the calibrated CN.

The MAE is calculated as follows:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |Q_{est} - Q_{obs}|}{n} \quad (28)$$

where Q_{est} is the estimated *direct runoff*, Q_{obs} is the observed *direct runoff*, and n is the number of events accounted for.

Table 4 shows the composited and calibrated CNs as well as the MAE for all three approaches with and without accounting for AMC.

First an analysis of the results without accounting for antecedent moisture conditions is presented. Generally, the estimated CNs were close to the calibrated CNs. The largest difference with 7.7 could be observed for the deforested watershed. No influence of the deforestation could be found for the calibrated CNs. On the contrary, the forested watershed has the highest calibrated CN. It can further be seen that the MAE was best for the forested watershed for all three approaches. The largest MAE for the calibrated approach for deforested watershed is the consequence of the relatively largest variability in precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour of this watershed. In the deforested and intermediately forested watershed the calibrated approach gave the best results. In the forested watershed the composited approach was slightly better indicating a sub-optimal CN for the simple calibration procedure. As there are only few values available (11, 11, and 16 events above 50mm) a sub-optimal calibration is not surprising. In the deforested watershed, the MAEs of the three approaches were very similar, indicating a that the optimal CN lies somewhere in between the composited and the calibrated CN.

For all watershed and approaches the MAE was higher when it was accounted for AMC. Interesting is especially the higher MAE of the calibrated approach compared to the composited approach in the forested watershed. This is indicating a sub-optimal CN for both approaches with an ideal CN in between. Also worth mentioning is the strong difference in MAE between the approaches in the deforested watershed with accounting for AMC compared to the small differences without accounting for AMC. Here, 8 out of 11 events were overestimated (6 out of 6 for AMC III). Thus, relatively lower CNs are giving a lower MAE. The calibrated CN was lower than the composited CN and the output of the distributed approach is per definition larger than for the composited approach.

Table 4. Number of precipitation events above 50mm, composited and calibrated CNs, and mean absolute error of the composited, the distributed, and the calibrated approach for the three Colombian watersheds.

	Number of events	Composited CN	Calibrated CN	MAE [mm] –	
				composited/distributed/calibrated Without AMC	With AMC
Deforested	11	73.0	65.3	12.7/12.9/12.3	15.3/19.0/13.1
Intermediately Forested	11	69.9	65.8	8.0/11.6/6.1	12.7/11.3/9.7
Forested	16	65.8	67.7	7.6/9.2/7.7	12.9/12.9/14.6

To analyse the consequence of applying the SCS-CN method continuously, as it was done for the water balance approach, the direct runoff for each day was determined. The sum-up of the estimated daily

direct runoffs for both approaches in comparison to the measured *direct runoff* over the whole investigation period can be found in the following table:

Table 5. Total estimated and measured direct runoff for the three Columbian watersheds over the investigation period between the 12.06.2014 and 30.05.2015 without and with accounting for AMC.

	Watershed	Deforested	Intermediately Forested	Forested
Total measured Q [mm]		1017	649	852
Total estimated Q [mm]	Without AMC	390	304	206
	With AMC	1131	1016	517

When using only CN_{II} , the estimated *direct runoff* was around two to four times lower than the measured *direct runoff*. This deviance can be attributed to the underestimation of the *direct runoff* for the small events caused by the secondary P effect (outside the near-constant CN range). When it was accounted for antecedent moisture conditions, the estimated total *direct runoff* was considerably higher than without accounting. This is due to the wet climate leading to a large number of precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs with AMC III. The total *direct runoff* was overestimated for the deforested and intermediately forested watershed and underestimated for the forested watershed. Large events with AMC III were generally underestimated and large events with AMC I were overestimated.

This analysis is largely dependent on the baseflow contribution component applied. With such a simple approach as applied in this study, errors of the computed *direct runoff* are expected to occur. For some small events these errors might lead to a *direct runoff* output when actually no *direct runoff* was occurring. On the contrary, it might also happen that no direct runoff is computed although it was occurring. This can for example happen, when precipitation is falling on 5 or more consecutive days. On one of the days, the *direct runoff* is set to 0mm when the Institute of Hydrology algorithm is applied. This is indicating that the above analysis of the estimated versus observed total *direct runoff* is just a rough indication of the validity of the SCS-CN method when applied continuously. Still, the trend towards underestimation of the total direct runoff without accounting for antecedent moisture conditions is in line with the expectations based on the secondary P effect.

Hjelmfelt et al. (1981) claimed that the CNs for AMC I and AMC III approximate the bounds at the 90% and 10% exceedance frequency of event-wise ideal CNs in the near-constant CN range, respectively. This claim was tested for the Columbian watersheds. The percentile of CN_I and CN_{III} were calculated as based on the MATLAB percentile function (MathWorks, 2021).

Table 6. Percent exceedance of the CN_I and CN_{III} in relation to the observed event-wise optimized CNs for the three Columbian watersheds for the calibrated CN.

Watershed	Deforested	Intermediately Forested	Forested
Exceedance for CN_I [%]	99	99	96
Exceedance for CN_{III} [%]	34	10	3

5. Case Study Region – Kenya

The WT was applied to three watersheds in the Ewaso Ng'iro basin close to the Mount Kenya. The watersheds were originally investigated by MacMillan (n.d.) in an unfinished doctoral thesis. Originally, the watersheds were selected as such to cover different LULC and climatic settings (see Table 7) (personal communication with Dr. Hanspeter Liniger, 28.06.2021). The discharge and precipitation data of the

watersheds were obtained from the Centre for Training and Integrated Research in ASAL Development (2021). Generally, the datasets had a low quality. Many dubious values or gaps exist. The land use and soil maps were adopted from the work of MacMillan (n.d.). The maps were only available as images in portable network (.png) format. As the projection of the maps was unknown, they were matched to the *Google Maps* imagery files using the Georeferencer Tool (QGIS.org, 2021) applying a Polynomial 1 transformation. This was done with the expert knowledge of Dr. Hanspeter Liniger who contributed to the creation of the maps and knows the region well (personal communication 15.07.2021).

Table 7. Name, area, elevation range, average precipitation and investigated time period of the three watersheds in Kenya.

Name	Area [km ²]	Elevation Range [m.a.s.l.]	Average Annual Precipitation [mm]*	Investigated Time Period
Mukogodo	2.44	1770 – 1890	395	01.03.1989 – 30.06.1998
Ngenia	1.3	2110 – 2220	695	01.02.1996 – 15.11.2000
Ituuri	8.08	2570 – 3620	851	22.04.1992 – 12.07.2000

*For measurement periods 01.03.1989 – 30.06.1998 (Mukogodo), 16.06.1989 – 30.04.2001 (Ngenia), and 22.04.1992 – 12.07.2000 (Ituuri) using Thiessen Polygon approach.

Based on the georeferenced land use and soil maps the WT was applied. Each unique connected combination of land usage and soil was considered as an HRU. Each HRU was assigned a CN based on Table 13. This table was developed by MacMillan (n.d.) specifically for the Kenyan context.

To account for the different rain gauges in the watersheds, the Thiessen Polygon method was applied which caused further fragmentation of the HRUs. Additionally, each HRU was assigned a mean slope [m/m] calculated based on a 30m×30m grid from SRTM (NASA JPL, 2013).

The rivers in the Mukogodo and Ituuri are ephemeral. The channels remain dry or at a very low level for most of the year. The Ngenia stream is also generally at a low level. In the case of large precipitation events, the streams grow by a multiple of their usual size (MacMillan, n.d.). For the Mukogodo and Ituuri watershed, baseflow contribution to the streamflow could be neglected due to its relative insignificance. In both cases, *direct runoff* was assumed to be equal to the streamflow. In the Ngenia watershed however, a baseflow abstraction was conducted due to a significant baseflow contribution in the years 1997 and 1998.

An analysis of the time series of precipitation and streamflow revealed that the stream usually needs two days until the precipitation is run off and for the stream to be back at a normal level. The reason for this behaviour could not be determined. To account for the behaviour, events were chosen based on the following criteria:

- a) Above 10mm daily precipitation;
- b) Not followed by a day with more than 5mm precipitation; and
- c) Not preceded by a day with more than 5mm precipitation.

Choosing this approach it was possible to prevent erroneous allocations of discharges to precipitation events. However, this approach also led to several events being excluded from the analysis.

For each event fulfilling the criteria mentioned above, the streamflow and the precipitation of the following day was added. On some days, one or more stations had data gaps. Therefore, only days for which all rain gauges had a valid value were considered in the analysis. The AMC for each day was determined using 5-days antecedent precipitation following the guidance provided by Table 1 for *Dry Season*.

In all three watersheds only a handful of events were observed that fulfilled $S = 2.19P$. In the Ituuri watershed none of the events was large enough. This makes it impossible to conduct a reasonable calibration for all watersheds.

In the following, the three watersheds and the results of the WT application are presented in detail.

(xvii) Mukogodo

The Mukogodo watershed is located on the semi-arid basement plateau. To the north of the watershed is gently sloped, rolling land. To the south the landscape is characterized by steep, rocky hills intersected with steep valleys. The majority of the area can be classified as hydrologic soil group B with some smaller areas belonging to soil groups A and C. (MacMillan, n.d.)

The following figures show the obtained soil and land use maps of the Mukogodo watershed. The *Thiessen Polygon* method was applied based on 5 rain gauges (NRM, B, C, D, and E).

Figure 22 (left) & Figure 23 (right). Hydrologic Soil Group and land use along MacMillan (n.d.), rain gauges, and Thiessen polygons in the Mukogodo watershed. (landuse legend from MacMillan (n.d.))

Figure 24 shows the measured streamflow and the obtained precipitation of the Mukogodo watershed. It can be observed that starting from spring 1996 the streamflow was substantially larger than in the years before even though the precipitation regime did not change. In many instances the streamflow is several times larger than the precipitation input. This suggests measurement errors. Therefore, the range indicated in pink in Figure 24 was excluded from further analysis.

Figure 24. Observed streamflow and precipitation for the Mukogodo watershed in Kenya. The part of the data that was not considered in the analysis is indicated in pink.

— Streamflow Measurements
 — Precipitation Measurements
 Excluded Data

Figure 25 shows the area (in percent) occupied by a certain CN range. Around 70% of the area has a CN of 70-80. These CNs generally occur for 2-20% treed bare or sparse grass and in combination with a soil type B. This combination covers most of the area of the watershed.

Figure 25. Percent area that has been assigned a certain CN_i range for the Mukogodo watershed.

Based on the output of the WT, the following 2nd order polynomial trendlines were obtained:

$$Q = 0.0047P^2 - 0.0648P - 0.3621 \text{ for } CN_{II} \quad (29)$$

$$Q = 0.0027P^2 - 0.1889P + 3.3623 \text{ for } CN_I \quad (30)$$

$$Q = 0.0051P^2 + 0.2665P - 2.1597 \text{ for } CN_{III} \quad (31)$$

Figure 26 shows the measured and simulated precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs above 10mm precipitation as well as the estimated P - Q -relationship. A major part of the events have AMC I. Above the 20mm precipitation threshold all events except one were inside the realm spanned by AMC I and AMC III. This indicates that the estimated CNs are quite accurate. This is however not surprising as the estimate table was created by MacMillan (n.d.) specifically for Kenyan settings.

Further it can be observed that this approach underestimated many of the smaller events. By having considered only events without a precipitation input of more than 5mm on the precedent day, it can be concluded that these events were not produced due to a lag between precipitation and *direct runoff*. Additionally, as in general no baseflow was found these events are also not the consequence of a wrong baseflow to *direct runoff* allocation. A possible explanation for this specific precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour might be the influence of soil crusting and degradation of grass cover over dry periods enhancing *direct runoff* as well as spatio-temporal variability in precipitation. Also, the influence of a secondary P effect has been considered.

Figure 26. Measured and simulated precipitation-direct runoff pairs and trendlines for the simulated pairs for CN_{II} , CN_I , and CN_{III} for the Mukogodo watershed.

- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{II}
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_I
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{III}
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_{II}
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_I
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_{III}
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{II}
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_I
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{III}

(xviii) Ngenia

The Ngenia watershed is the flattest of the three watersheds. 92% of the area has a slope of less than 0.05m/m. Its shape is elongated, and the landscape is characterized by undulating land with flattish ridge tops. Its land use is dominated by crop (maize, beans, potato, wheat) and grassland. A major part (87%) of the watershed has been classified as hydrologic soil group B. 13% of the area has a hydrologic soil group C. (MacMillan, n.d.)

The following figures show the obtained soil and land use map of the Ngenia watershed. The *Thiessen Polygon* method was applied based on 5 rain gauges (NRM, B, C, D, and E).

Figure 27. Hydrologic Soil Group along MacMillan (n.d.), rain gauges, and Thiessen polygons in the Ngenia watershed.

Figure 28. Land use / Land cover along MacMillan (n.d.) of the Ngenia watershed. (legend from MacMillan (n.d.))

Figure 29 shows the measured streamflow and the obtained precipitation of the Ngenia watershed. It can be observed that between October 1997 and January 1998 and again in autumn 1998 two wet periods occurred. During this period, precipitation fell on the Ngenia watershed with unusual frequency and intensity. In period between 05.10.1997 and 15.01.1998 in total 783mm of precipitation was measured. This is more than the average yearly precipitation observed between 16.06.1989 and 30.04.2001 (see Table 7). As a result, a constant streamflow could be observed. Smaller precipitation events began to create *direct runoff*.

In contrast to the other two watersheds a substantial baseflow component appeared. In the relatively wet periods, a continuous streamflow could be observed. The baseflow was calculated using the Institute

of Hydrology (1980) approach as described in section 4. The obtained baseflow contribution is also shown in Figure 29. In November and December 1997 the assumed baseflow contribution was around 10mm.

Figure 29. Observed streamflow, observed precipitation, and calculated baseflow contribution for the Ngenia watershed in Kenya.

- Streamflow Measurements
- Calculated Baseflow Contribution
- Precipitation Measurements

Figure 30 shows the area (in percent) occupied by a certain CN range. Around half of the watershed has a CN between 70 and 75. To a large degree this is caused by the cropland in the upper part of the watershed.

Figure 30. Percent area that has been assigned a certain CN_i range for the Ngenia watershed.

Based on the output of the WT, the following 2nd order polynomials were obtained:

$$Q = 0.0152P^2 - 0.3966P + 2.0666 \text{ for } CN_{II} \quad (32)$$

$$Q = 0.078P^2 - 0.65P + 13.681 \text{ for } CN_I \quad (33)$$

$$Q = 0.0189P^2 + 0.3868 - 4.4295 \text{ for } CN_{III} \quad (34)$$

Figure 31 shows the measured and simulated precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs above 10mm precipitation as well as the estimated P - Q -relationship. A major part of the events have AMC III. The reason for this is a specific precipitation regime, where very dry periods are followed by lengthy wet periods (from several days to weeks). This contrasts with the Mukogodo watershed where intense precipitation occurs only on one or two consecutive days. Therefore, due to the exclusion criteria a larger number of events were excluded for the Ngenia watershed.

Generally, the results need to be interpreted with caution. For the two largest events, the *direct runoff* significantly overshoot the precipitation input. This might be due to an erroneous level-to-streamflow relationship leading to an overestimation of the streamflow (similarly to what was observed in the Mukogodo watershed for the years 1996 to 1998). An argument supporting the estimated precipitation-streamflow relationship are the measured precipitation-direct runoff data from the years 1989 to 1993 prepared by MacMillan (n.d.). The maximum observed *direct runoff* was 15mm for a precipitation event of around 75mm. In contrast, on the 04.10.1998 an event of 11mm led to 11mm *direct runoff*. It is not possible to distinguish between the influence of the wet seasons in 1997 and 1998 and the errors in the level to streamflow relationship.

Figure 31. Measured and simulated precipitation-direct runoff pairs and trendlines for the simulated pairs for CN_{II} , CN_I , and CN_{III} for the Ngenia watershed.

- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{II}
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_I
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{III}
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_{II}
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_I
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_{III}
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{II}
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_I
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{III}

(xix) Ituuri

The Ituuri watershed is a longitudinal watershed on the north-western upper slopes of the Month Kenya. It has three different vegetational zones – a moorland zone in the uplands, a small-scale cropping zone in the middle, and a lower large scale crop zone in the lower part. The slopes are steep (70% in the range of 0.05 to 0.16m/m, and 19% in the range of 16 to 43m/m). The soils of the watershed lie on volcanic deposits and contain well drained soils of hydrologic soil groups A and B. Furthermore, the watershed can be divided into two vegetation zones. In the upper watershed a natural cover of treed good grass dominates whereas in the lower part cropland predominates. (MacMillan, n.d.)

The following figures show the obtained soil and land use maps of the Ituuri watershed. The *Thiessen Polygon* method was applied based on 4 rain gauges (A, B, C, Karuri). In this application the Karuri gauge determines the precipitation input as it occupies around 66% of the area.

Figure 32 (left) & Figure 33 (right). Hydrologic Soil Group and landuse along MacMillan (n.d.), rain gauges, and Thiessen polygons in the Ituri watershed. (landuse legend from MacMillan (n.d.))

Figure 34 shows the measured streamflow and the obtained precipitation of the Ituri watershed. The Ituri watershed has the highest annual precipitation input of the three Kenyan watersheds. The largest events (with 50-60mm) are of the same intensity as the largest events observed for the Mukogodo and Ituri watersheds.

Figure 34. Observed streamflow and precipitation for the Ituri watershed in Kenya.

— Streamflow Measurements
— Precipitation Measurements

Figure 35 shows the area (in percent) occupied by a certain CN range. Around 40% of the area has an CN between 70 and 75, due to the cropland in the lower part of the watershed. The rest of the area has a CN below 70.

Figure 35. Percent area that has been assigned a certain CN_{II} range for the Ituri watershed.

Based on the output of the WT, the following 2nd order polynomials were obtained:

$$Q = 0.0029P^2 - 0.068P + 0.1793 \text{ for } CN_{II} \quad (35)$$

$$Q = 0.0017P^2 - 0.1425P + 2.9632 \text{ for } CN_I \quad (36)$$

$$Q = 0.0041P^2 + 0.0797P - 1.2758 \text{ for } CN_{III} \quad (37)$$

Figure 36 shows the measured and simulated precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs above 10mm precipitation as well as the estimated P - Q -relationship. It can be observed the observed *direct runoff*, with a maximum of 14mm for the largest observed precipitation event of 65mm, was relatively low compared to the two other Kenyan watersheds. This aligns to the fact that the Ngenia watershed has the lowest CNs of the analysed Kenyan watersheds. As for the Mukogodo watershed, no correlation can be found between the AMC and precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour. Also, the estimates of the tables were accurate: for events above 20mm only one was outside the boundaries spanned by AMC I and AMC III. But again, this should not be surprising as the tables were created for this exact region.

Figure 36. Measured and simulated precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs and trendlines for the simulated pairs for CN_{II} , CN_I , and CN_{III} for the Ituuiri watershed.

- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{II}
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_I
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{III}
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_{II}
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_I
- ◆ Estimated Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs CN_{III}
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{II}
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_I
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{III}

6. Case Study Region– Switzerland

The SCS-CN methodology was applied to multiple watersheds in Switzerland. Daily precipitation data from RhiresD prepared from the Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology (MeteoSwiss) were averaged over the investigated watersheds (MeteoSwiss, 2019). Daily streamflow data and the corresponding watershed shape files provided by the Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) were used (Bundesamt für Umwelt, 2020). The soil map was adopted from Ross et al. (2018). The land use map was taken from Bundesamt für Statistik (2017) and contains 46 different land use categories. To each category a combination of land use and hydrologic condition (as implemented in the WT) was allocated (see Appendix, Table 16). This allocation was done with the expert knowledge of Dr. Hanspeter Liniger (personal communication, 05.07.2021). To determine the CNs it was distinguished between the months of April, May, and October and the months between June to September. Colder months were excluded from the analysis to keep the amount of snow precipitation low. The investigated watersheds were chosen based on the following conditions:

- a) Area smaller than 100km²;
- b) No glacier inside the watershed;
- c) No lake inside the watershed; and
- d) Unperturbed by infrastructure.

11 watersheds meeting the criteria were identified:

Table 8. Investigated Swiss watersheds and their ID along Bundesamt für Umwelt, Abteilung Hydrologie (2020).

Watershed Name	ID
Rotenbach – Plaffeien, Schwyberg	2251
Minster – Euthal, Rüti	2300
Glatt – Herisau, Zellermühle	2305
Langeten – Huttwil, Häberenberg	2343
Necker – Mogelsberg, Aachsäge	2374
Chli Schliere – Alpnach, Chilch Erli	2436
Veveyse – Vevey, Copet	2486
Biber – Biberbrugg	2604
Sellenbodenbach -Neuenkirch	2608
Alp – Einsiedeln	2609
Scheulte – Vicques	2610

The *direct runoff* was calculated from the measured streamflow using the baseflow separation approach described by the Institute of Hydrology (1980) as applied by Tallaksen & van Lanen (2004). In the following, the obtained *direct runoff* is called “measured *direct runoff*”.

The *direct runoff* was estimated for three different applications of the SCS-CN method – the distributed (i), the composited (ii), and the calibrated (iii) approach.

- (i) Using the distributed approach the *direct runoff* was estimated in the following way:
 - (1) The number of cells inside the watershed with a given combination of land use and hydrologic soil group were obtained.

- (2) The CN_I and CN_{III} for each combination of land use and hydrologic soil group was determined using Appendix, Table 16. *Growing Season* conditions were chosen for setting the thresholds of precipitation for AMC I, AMC II, or AMC III.³
- (3) The *direct runoff* for each combination of land use and hydrologic soil group and for AMC I, AMC II, and AMC III was calculated for ten precipitation inputs ranging from 50mm to 140mm with an interval of 10mm.
- (4) The obtained *direct runoff* for each of the precipitation inputs and combination of land use and hydrologic soil group was added up following equation (10).
- (5) A function simulating the *direct runoff* over the whole range between 50 and 140mm was determined for AMC I, AMC II, and AMC III. This was achieved by fitting a 2nd order polynomial to the obtained precipitation-*direct runoff* points for the different precipitation inputs using the method of least squares.

The functions used for estimating the direct runoff over the range from 50 to 140mm for the distributed approach for all the investigated watersheds can be found in Appendix, Table 15.

- (ii) For the composited approach the following steps were conducted:
 - (1) The number of cells inside the watershed with a given combination of land use and hydrologic soil group were obtained.
 - (2) The CN_I , CN_{II} , and CN_{III} for each combination of land use and hydrologic soil group was determined using Appendix, Table 16. *Growing Season* conditions were chosen for setting the thresholds of precipitation for AMC I, AMC II, or AMC III.¹
 - (3) The CN_I , CN_{II} , and CN_{III} of the whole watershed was determined using equation (9).
- (iii) A calibration procedure following the storm event approach (see section (ix), equation (14)) was conducted. The calibrated CN for each watershed was determined as the mean optimal CN for all events above 50mm precipitation. The value of 50mm as the threshold was chosen trading-off the criterion defined by Hawkins et al. (1985) (see equation (11)) which is sometimes not met with this threshold, and the requirement for sufficient datapoints for all watersheds. The calibration procedure was conducted three times. Once with all data points, once for the events in April, May, and October, and once with events that occurred between June and September.

Table 10 shows the CNs obtained for the composited and calibrated approach and the *direct runoff* for all approaches. Additionally, the area [km²] and the average slope [m/m] and the number of events above 50mm are presented. For April, May, October the composited CNs for all watersheds are in a range from 77 to 82. From June to September the CNs were all in a range from 75 to 79.

Figure 37, Figure 38, and Figure 39 show the measured precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs as well as the estimated relationship for the three approaches for the Alp – Einsiedeln (2609) watershed. The same graphs for the other investigated watersheds can be found in the Digital Appendix, Switzerland\Figures. For the composited and the distributed approach, it is distinguished between April, May, and October and June-September. For the calibrated approach, the function that was obtained for all the events between April to October is shown.

³ This decision was taken with the consultation of Hanspeter Liniger (personal communication 05.07.2021).

The graphs have the following legend:

- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{II} , April, May, October
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_I , April, May, October
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{III} , April, May, October
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{II} , June-September
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_I , June-September
- Interpolated Direct Runoff Function CN_{III} , June-September
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{II} , June-September
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_I , June-September
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{III} , June-September
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{II} , April, May, October
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_I , April, May, October
- Measured Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs AMC_{III} , April, May, October

Figure 37. Measured precipitation-direct runoff pairs and trendlines for CN_{II} , CN_I , and CN_{III} for the Alp-Einsiedeln (2609) watershed with the composited approach.

Figure 38. Measured precipitation-direct runoff pairs and trendlines for CN_{I} , CN_{II} , and CN_{III} for the Alp-Einsiedeln (2609) watershed with the distributed approach.

Figure 39. Measured precipitation-direct runoff pairs and trendlines for CN_{I} , CN_{II} , and CN_{III} for the Alp-Einsiedeln (2609) watershed with the calibrated approach.

From Figure 37, Figure 38, and Figure 39 as well as from the figures in Digital Appendix, Switzerland\Figures it can be observed, that the precipitation-*direct runoff* relationship is generally independent from the 5-days antecedent precipitation. Also, the assumption of *Growing Season* led to a large part of the events having AMCI.

To check the accuracy of the simulations, the MAE between the observed and simulated *direct runoff* for all precipitation events above 50mm was determined with equation (29).

This analysis was conducted twice, once with accounting for antecedent moisture conditions and once without. In the ‘accounting’ analysis, the MAEs were determined applying the measured precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs against the corresponding function for either AMC_I, AMC_{II}, or AMC_{III}, depending on the measured 5-days antecedent precipitation along Table 1. In the ‘without accounting’ analysis, the MAEs were determined applying the measured precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs against the corresponding value determined for AMC_{II}.

For the calibrated approach the MAE was obtained by comparing all the measured precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs with the corresponding estimation for the months between April and October. For the composited and distributed approach, it was again distinguished between April, May, and October and June-September. This implies the MAE for an event that occurred in April, May, or October is determined using the corresponding function.

Table 10 shows the resulting CNs for the composited and calibrated approach and the MAEs for all the investigated approaches. Several observations can be made:

- The calibrated approach has for all watersheds lower or equal MAEs compared to both the composited and the distributed approach.
- The distributed approach often preforms better than the composited approach. In all cases, except for watershed 2343, the distributed CN approach had lower MAEs than the composited approach (without accounting for AMC).
- The MAE was in all cases lower when not accounting for AMC.
- For 7 of the 11 investigated watersheds the calibrated CN for April, May, and October was lower than the one for June-September.

Figure 40 and Figure 41 show the obtained composited and the calibrated CN for all investigated watersheds in Switzerland for April, May, and October and June to September respectively. It can be observed that 10 out of 11 watersheds remain relatively close to the 1:1-line which indicates a good correlation between the composited and the calibrated CNs. The watershed 2343 Langeten – Huttwil, Häberenbad stands out. The composited CN of this watershed is around 13 (AMO) and 10 (J-S) lower than the calibrated CN.

Table 9 shows the MAE of the composited CNs for all the watersheds.

Table 9. Mean absolute error of the composited CN compared to the calibrated CN.

Case	MAE
April, May, October	3.4
June - September	5.0

Figure 40. Calibrated and compositd CN for all investigated watersheds in Switzerland for April, May, and October.

● $CN_{Com}-CN_{Cal}$ -pairs
 — 1:1 Line

Figure 41. Calibrated and compositd CN for all investigated watersheds in Switzerland for June to September.

● $CN_{Com}-CN_{Cal}$ -pairs
 — 1:1 Line

Table 10. Watershed ID along Bundesamt für Umwelt, Abteilung Hydrologie (2020), area [km²], average slope [m/m], number precipitation events above 50mm per day over the whole measurement period, composited and calibrated CNs for the periods June to September (J-S) and April, May, and October (AMO), and mean absolute error of the estimations (obtained from distributed and composited approach and with calibration).

Watershed ID	Area [km ²]	Average Slope [m/m]	# events above 50mm	Composited CN _{II} – AMO	Composited CN _{II} – J-S	Calibrated CN _{II} – all / AMO / J-S	Mean Absolute Error [mm] – With / Without accounting for AMC		
							Composited	Distributed	Calibrated
2251	1.69	0.26	50	81.72	77.91	80.85 / 80.65 / 81.49	17.82 / 13.31	17.95 / 13.19	16.78 / 13.07
2300	59.1	0.37	125	80.48	77.14	80.67 / 82.09 / 76.36	16.17 / 12.41	15.81 / 12.21	15.57 / 11.28
2305	16.7	0.22	42	80.52	78.65	80.55 / 79.87 / 82.74	17.75 / 11.38	18.18 / 11.41	17.27 / 11.37
2343	59.9	0.18	23	80.25	78.09	67.39 / 66.95 / 68.66	10.45 / 8.13	12.96 / 8.21	6.92 / 2.48
2374	88.2	0.29	60	81.26	77.68	82.14 / 81.62 / 84.21	17.66 / 11.13	17.54 / 10.77	15.29 / 10.14
2436	21.6	0.46	67	77.51	74.97	78.54 / 82.95 / 70.11	20.13 / 16.24	19.46 / 16.14	19.40 / 15.39
2486	64.5	0.32	26	78.96	76.27	78.66 / 78.17 / 80.69	12.50 / 7.95	11.33 / 7.62	11.29 / 7.62
2604	31.9	0.23	49	77.58	75.38	82.00 / 81.69 / 82.75	15.95 / 10.06	14.96 / 8.80	13.31 / 7.37
2608	10.5	0.10	13	80.11	77.87	81.72 / 84.05 / 77.98	16.80 / 10.52	17.76 / 9.63	14.78 / 9.17
2609	46.6	0.31	58	77.99	75.44	82.92 / 83.16 / 82.33	18.10 / 12.75	17.13 / 11.79	15.78 / 9.54
2610	72.8	0.35	19	78.59	76.01	81.00 / 79.54 / 83.48	18.95 / 10.31	18.11 / 9.59	16.48 / 9.32
					Average		16.58 / 11.29	16.47 / 10.85	14.80 / 9.70

Based on the individually optimized CNs for the measured P - Q -pairs above a 50mm precipitation, the percentile of exceedance that CN_I and CN_{III} approach were determined. This analysis was conducted to compare the variability of the investigated Swiss watersheds and test the statement of Hjelmfelt et al. (1981) who claimed that CN_I and CN_{III} approximate the bounds at the 10th and 90th percentile of the empirically determined log-normal distribution function, respectively (see section (vi)). The percentile of CN_I and CN_{III} were calculated as based on the MATLAB percentile function (MathWorks, 2021). The results of this analysis can be found in the Appendix, Table 12. The following graph depicts the results graphically in analogy to Figure 7:

Figure 42. Comparison of CNs for 10% and 90% exceedance frequency with those for AMC I and AMC III for the 11 investigated Swiss watersheds.

It can be observed that for the investigated Swiss watersheds, the claim by Hjelmfelt et al. (1981) was accurate for the investigated Swiss watersheds. On average, CN_I and CN_{III} approximated the bounds at the 12th and 91st percentile of the set of optimal CNs, respectively.

Again watershed 2343 stands out as the individually optimized CNs occupy only a very narrow range (see Figure 43). None of the 23 individually optimized CNs is outside of the boundaries being spanned by CN_I and CN_{III} .

Figure 43. Measured precipitation-direct runoff pairs and estimated curves for CN_{I} , CN_{II} , and CN_{III} for the Langeten – Huttwil, Häberenbad (2343) watershed with the calibrated approach.

7. Discussion & Conclusion

(xx) What is the Validity of the SCS-CN Method?

Generally, in order to assess the validity of the SCS-CN method one has to answer the following question:

How accurate is the SCS-CN method in estimating P-Q-pairs?

However, as SCS-CN method can be applied in many different forms and as its conceptual framework has different interpretations one has to consider several factors when assessing the validity. First, one has to make a distinction between the calibrated and uncalibrated case (adopted from tables or from similar watersheds). Additionally, the form of the SCS-CN method (i.e. with/ without AMC accounting, with / without slope accounting, the value chose for the constant λ , composited / distributed approach, etc.) and the environmental settings (area, slope, climate, LULC, etc.) must be considered. Additionally, also that the precipitation range for which a validity assessment is conducted needs to be taken into account. This is particularly important as watersheds usually display a secondary P effect. This suggests that small storms are best reproduced by using higher CNs and large storms by using smaller CNs (for standard and complacent behaviour).

In the following, a validity assessment for the uncalibrated (a) and calibrated (b) case is conducted:

(a) Uncalibrated Case?

In the uncalibrated case, two possible sources of error exist that could affect the validity of the SCS-CN method. The first is the inherent variability of the watershed response to precipitation inputs. This error cannot be removed through calibration but only by changing the modelling framework (for example,

when using a SCS-CN method that accounts for other sources of variability). The second are the selection of sub-optimal parameters. This raises the question

1) *How accurate are the estimates of the representative CNs in the uncalibrated case?*

It has been shown in section (x) that the NEH-4 tables often do not provide accurate estimates. Often, the estimated CNs are far off the CNs that would accurately describe the observed precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour. As the WT relies on these estimates it has to be expected that it will produce in many cases inaccurate estimates of the precipitation-*direct runoff* relationship.

(b) Calibrated Case?

Watersheds have an inherent variability in their response to precipitation events. This variability can come from different sources. However, the SCS-CN method cannot isolate the impact of these sources on the variability in its simplistic approach. Therefore, even if the SCS-CN method is optimally calibrated, an error remains. The question arises:

2) *How accurate are the P-Q-pair estimates produced by the calibrated model?*

The original SCS-method only accounted for three different stages of antecedent soil moisture and could not account for other sources of variability. Therefore, to obtain a quantitative measure of the variability, several authors have suggested to consider the CN as a random variable. In this case, the question changes to:

3) *How similar is the observed distribution of CNs to the predicted distribution?*

Answering this question requires large data sets, which translates into long observation periods, further complicated through constraints of applying the SCS-CN method to intense precipitation events. When assuming the CN to be a random variable, the validity of the SCS-CN for single events can be described based on the distribution function.

(xxi) Validity of the SCS-CN Method in the Case Study Regions

In the following, the results from the three case studies will be analysed against the questions raised in section (xx):

2) *How accurate are the P-Q-pair estimates produced by the calibrated model?*

In the Switzerland case study region, the average MAE for the calibrated CN was 9.7mm. 9 out of 11 investigated watersheds had a MAE between 7 and 13mm. This difference comes from the inherent variability of the underlying processes that are not accounted for and the quality of the data. The estimated *direct runoffs* were usually between 20mm and 50mm. Thus, the average error was between 20 to 50% of the estimated *direct runoff*, depending on the intensity of the precipitation event. Single events however often vary strongly.

In the Columbia case study region, the MAEs for the calibrated approach and the three watersheds were 12.3mm (deforested), 6.1mm (intermediately forested), and 7.7mm (forested). The relatively high MAE for the deforested watershed can be explained by a larger variability. For the forested and deforested watershed, the calibrated CN were slightly under the optimal CN. These sub-optimal CNs are likely due to the simple calibration approach and the few observed events above 50mm.

In the Kenya case study region the lack of large events made it impossible to reasonably calibrate the model assuming a constant CN over a large range of precipitation inputs. Still, it can be observed that in the Mukogodo and Ituuri watersheds the large events are to a large part in the bound spanned by AMC I and AMC III. This indicates a common variability.

1) *How accurate are the estimates of the representative CNs in the uncalibrated case?*

Both, in the Switzerland and the Columbia case study region, for most instances the CN estimates fit the calibrated CNs well. Only for one Swiss watershed, the estimated CN deviated strongly from the calibrated CN. In the Switzerland case study region, the average MAE for the distributed and the composited approach was 10.85mm and 11.29mm, respectively. Thus, estimating the CN led only to a minor increase in MAE compared to the calibrated CN.

Also, in the Columbia case study region, the CN estimate proved to be good. For the forested and deforested watershed, the MAE for the composited and distributed approach practically remained at the same value as for the calibrated approach. The MAE for the intermediately forested watershed increased slightly by 2mm (composited) and by 5mm (distributed). However, in both cases the calibrated CN estimate was a bit lower compared to the ideal CN. Thus, the *direct runoff* estimates for the forested and deforested watershed were a bit too high. In the intermediately forested watershed, the CN was also slightly overestimated.

In the Kenya case study region, the tables were specifically created for this exact region. The estimated CNs matched well the observations for the Mukogodo and the Ituuri watershed. For the Ngenia watershed no conclusive statement can be made as the measured direct runoff is likely to be largely overestimated.

3) *How similar is the observed distribution of CNs to the predicted distribution?*

In the Switzerland case study region, CN_I and CN_{III} on average approximated the bounds at the 12th and 91st percentile of the set of optimal CNs, respectively. This is in accordance with the claim of Hjelmfelt et al. (1981). Furthermore, the variation of the individual watersheds around these bounds was reasonable. The Columbia case study region showed a similar tendency, however to conduct a reliable assessment additional data on events above 50mm would be required.

(xxii) Validity of the SCS-CN Method in different Biomes and Climatic Settings

The precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour on which the SCS-CN is based on has originally been used for small to medium-sized humid agricultural watersheds in the U.S. Several studies around the world have shown that the SCS-CN method also applies to other biomes and climatic settings, as for example in the Columbia and the Switzerland case study regions. However, one needs to understand, how are different biomes and climatic settings affecting the validity of the SCS-CN method. Again, the validity assessment needs to be conducted for both the calibrated and uncalibrated case.

(a) Uncalibrated Case

An essential question for the validity assessment of the uncalibrated case is: *How accurate are the estimations of the representative CNs?* In the context of varying biomes and climatic settings, this question changes to: *How are the CN estimations changing with different biome or climate?*

Concerning varying biomes, Hawkins et al. (1984) (see section (x)) have shown that the CN estimates are most accurate for agricultural watersheds and least accurate for forested watersheds. This indicates that estimation errors are likely to occur for forested watersheds.

Concerning the influence of climate, the relative influence and intensity of the sources of variability in the precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour can vary significantly. The “typical storm” is different around the world. This affects the response of the watersheds. Short and intense storms are likely to increase *direct runoff* and thus might have a higher representative CN. Also, the long-term precipitation is likely to affect the precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour. For example very dry regions might cause crusting of the soil which is leading to an intensification of *runoff*.

(b) Calibrated Case

Watersheds have a certain variability in their precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour. With their CN defined as a random variable several authors have quantified a typical variability. By investigating the influence

of varying biomes and climatic settings the question *How similar is the observed distribution of CNs to the predicted distribution?* is now dependent on the following question: *How is the precipitation-direct runoff variability changing with different biome or climate?*

To conduct a reliable calibration sufficient data on large events are needed. As mentioned, the application of the SCS-method should be limited to events fulfilling $S = 2.19P$. This restricts the calibration procedure to watersheds that have enough large events, which depends on the climate. In the Kenya case study region, only very few events satisfying the criterion were observed. Therefore, to conduct a reliable calibration procedure a dataset over a very long period of time (several decades) is needed. This compares to the Columbia case study region where in a period of less than a year many events fulfilling the criterion were observed. Here, the precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour can well be identified by using data covering a relatively short duration.

An important source of variability that can have a strong influence on the precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour of a watershed is the arrangement and connectivity of different zones in the watershed. This could also explain the relatively higher variability in precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour in the deforested watershed compared to the intermediately forested and the forested watershed in the Columbia case study region.⁴ As the deforested area was close to the outlet of the deforested watershed, it is likely that the variability in the precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour was caused by the precipitation variability over the watershed. This effect should not be underestimated for small heterogeneous watersheds.

(xxiii) AMC Accounting

Generally, no correlation between the determined AMC and precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour could be observed. Accounting for AMC often leads to significant estimation errors and it is therefore not recommended. This means that also model adaptations such as the one by Mishra et al. (2002) presenting a continuous AMC accounting (see equations (15) and (16)) are unlikely to improve the performance of the model. Nonetheless, while the antecedent moisture conditions might indeed have a significant influence on precipitation-*direct runoff* behaviour, the 5-days antecedent precipitation is not a good proxy. Other methods to account for the antecedent soil moisture such as in the SWAT model might however be more accurate and improve the model. (see Appendix, Surface Runoff Component of the Soil & Water Assessment Tool)

(xxiv) The Composite vs. Distributed CN Approach

The NEH-4 recommends using the composite CN approach. However, this is criticised by Grove et al. (1998) because it underestimates the direct runoff compared to the distributed approach. However, it is not surprising that the NEH-4 does not recommend using a distributed CN approach as this would imply that the SCS-CN method can be applied on the point scale. Accepting this would be conceptually incompatible with the notion that the SCS-CN calculates the direct runoff only on the watershed scale (see section (xii)). Thus, the discussion on the use of composite versus distributed CNs is a direct consequence of the discussion about what the SCS-CN actually calculates – surface or *direct runoff*.

Grove et al. (1998) state that the composite CN approach was only developed to save time. However, this claim is not entirely true. The compositing of the CNs is an inevitable consequence of the way the method has been developed. It is conceptually not conceivable to change the perspective of the method to as distributed view. Therefore, rather than just being a time-saver, the composite CN approach is a conceptual necessity. Only if the definition of what the SCS-CN actually calculates changes it would be conceptually accurate to apply the distributed CN approach.

⁴ As mentioned, another explanation might be the variability of vegetation growth throughout the year in the deforested area.

In their critique of the composite CN approach, Grove et al. (1998) start with the assumption that the SCS-CN method is a point scale infiltration method. From this conceptually different perspective it appears correct to state that the SCS-CN method underestimates the *runoff*. However, as the SCS-CN method was originally developed based on watershed scale data the perspective shifts – the distributed CN approach does not underestimate but the distributed CN approach overestimates the CN.

Still, Grove et al. (1998) well examines the conceptual challenges of CN compositing. With CN compositing, the exponential nature of the SCS-CN method is ignored. This can lead to significant differences between the composited and distributed approach. These differences grow with increasing differences of the CNs in the watershed.

In the Switzerland case study region, the distributed CN approach performed better than the composited approach for 9 out of 11 watersheds without accounting for AMC and for 7 out of 11 with accounting for AMC. The reason, why the composited approach generally performed better for the Swiss watersheds can be explained by the fact that the table estimates generally underestimated the calibrated CN. As the composited approach always produces less *direct runoff* than the distributed approach, the distributed approach compensated this underestimation. This is also the reason why for the watershed with the ID 2343 the composited approach was better – here the CN was overestimated. Still, both approaches delivered reasonable results. On average, the composited approach performed only 0.11mm (with AMC) and 0.41mm (without AMC) worse than the distributed approach.

In the Columbia case study region, the composited CN approach performed better for all three watersheds. Here, the table estimates overestimated the CNs. Thus, the lower composited CN gave better results than the distributed CN.

No final conclusion can be made on whether one of the approaches performs significantly better than the other. The individual performance of the two approaches ultimately depends on the initial CN estimates. If the composited CN estimate is too low, the *direct runoff* is underestimated. In such a case, the distributed CN approach performs usually better as the *direct runoff* is higher. The contrary is true for overestimations.

Several claims about the SCS-CN were investigated that were based on the original concept of the SCS-CN method (i.e. composite CN, only for large precipitation events). This raises the question whether these are also important and correct for the distributed approach:

- The secondary P effect is a watershed behaviour. It does not depend on the model applied.
- The estimation of CNs is different for the two approaches. The analysis conducted in section (x) is only valid for the composited approach. However, as the distributed approach always delivers larger *direct runoffs* than the composite approach, the distributed CNs for the watersheds that are overestimated with the composited approach will even be more overestimated.
- That AMC I and AMC III approximate the 90th and 10th percentile of exceedance frequency can only be claimed for one single CN. This idea is only conceivable when a composite approach is chosen.

(xxv) Watershed Response Behaviour

From the watershed responses shown in the Digital Appendix, Columbia\Watershed Response, Kenya\Watershed Response, and Switzerland\Figures it can be observed that some watersheds appear to follow a complacent behaviour. Examples are the watersheds with IDs 2300 and 2343 in Switzerland, the forested watershed in the Columbia case study region, or the Mukogodo watershed in the Kenya case study region. Generally, the application of the SCS-CN method is not recommended for these watersheds. However, as the curve is generally getting flatter with increasing precipitation and the calibration procedure produces a CN that is in between the range of ideal CNs, the acceptable *direct runoff* estimates could nonetheless be obtained.

Another interesting behaviour was observed for the watersheds with the IDs 2608 and 2436. For large events, both experienced a rise with increasing precipitation. This behaviour has not been described by Hawkins (1993).

(xxvi) Large Watersheds in Kenya – Joss (2018)

In his work, Joss (2018) applied the SCS-CN method to very large areas. The areas were then further split up into different HRUs each contributing to one channel. To obtain the total *runoff* at the outlet of the large watersheds, the individual *runoffs* were simply summed up. This is problematic as channel transmission losses are increasing with increasing watershed size (see section (viii), (4)). Additionally, in the warm climate of Kenya also evaporation might have an impact. While the SWAT model also subdivides large watersheds into smaller LSUs and HRU, the streamflow is then routed by accounting for channel transmission losses.

(xxvii) Cormier Watershed in Haiti – Eichenberger (2019)

A very good example, of how the WT should be applied is given by Eichenberger (2019). In this study, the tool is used to investigate the influence of LULC on floods. On the basis of different extreme LULC scenarios, the WT allows to exemplify well the importance of sustainable land management in this case. Also, the study was conducted on an agricultural area for which it has been shown that the CN estimates are most accurate.

(xxviii) The Water Balance Approach - Bandy (2020)

The water balance approach described in section (xvi) is questionable due to several reasons:

- Conceptually, the water balance approach calculates the infiltration with equation (20): $F = P - Q$. However, this is in contradiction to the assumption behind the SCS-CN methodology as stated by equation (1), namely $F = P - I_a - Q$. The water balance approach neglects I_a . Instead an evaporation part is included that takes over the role of the I_a .
- Applying the SCS-CN methodology to events below the threshold of $S \leq 2.19P$ is not recommended. Applying the SCS-CN to events below the threshold, likely underestimates the *direct runoff* (for watersheds exhibiting complacent of standard behaviour, conversely for violent behaviour) and hence the infiltration is likely to be overestimated.
- The water balance approach leverages the SWAT AMC accounting (see equations (17) and (18)). These equations cause CN_I and CN_{III} to move even further away from CN_{II} than the original equations in the NEH-4 (see equation (7) and (8)). This approach is questionable, as SWAT itself does not use AMC I and AMC III directly but creates a connection between soil moisture and AMC (see Appendix, *Surface Runoff Component of the Soil & Water Assessment Tool*). However, the implementation of the SWAT equations for AMC accounting in the WT itself is correct, as it is only used in the process of slope accounting. Sharpley & Williams Slope accounting implemented in the WT is based on equation (18).

(xxix) Continuous Application of SCS-CN Method – Columbia Case Study Region

The analysis of the three Columbian watersheds has shown that the continuous application of the SCS-CN method does lead to significant estimation errors in the long-term *direct runoff*. Table 5 shows that the estimated total *direct runoff* was around two to four times lower than the total measured *direct runoff* when not accounting for AMC. Contrarily, when AMC was accounted for, the total *direct runoff* was overestimated in two of three cases, but in general the estimates were more accurate. The likely reason for achieving better results by accounting for AMC is that due to the wet climate many days were assigned AMC III. In consequence, accounting for AMC leads to higher applied CNs and to higher *direct runoff* estimates. This effect is specific to wet climate. In dry climate with a lot of AMC I days, accounting for AMC would lead to the opposite – decreasing the long-term *direct runoff*.

(xxx) SWAT – Continuous Application of the CN method

On the applicability of SWAT, the developers state: “SWAT is a continuous model, i.e. a long-term yield model. The model is not designed to simulate detailed, single-event flood routing.” (Nietsch et al., 2009, p.2) This statement contradicts NEH-4: “Curve numbers were originally developed from annual flood flows from experimental watersheds, and their application to low flows or small flood peak flows is not recommended.” (SCS, 2004, p. 10-19)

The watershed response for small and large precipitation events is not optimally modelled by the same CN due to the secondary P effect. Hence, if the SCS-CN is applied continuously, estimation errors will occur. If the calibrated CN is larger than the optimal CN for a given event, the *direct runoff* will be overestimated for standard and complacent behaviour. Hence, large events will be overestimated, and small events will be underestimated. In the case of violent behaviour, the opposite is true.

As seen above, the SWAT model uses the SCN-CN method for a purpose it was not developed for. However, by specifying that the SWAT model is only suitable for modelling long term water flows and yields, this problem is mitigated. In the calibration procedure a CN is found for each HRU. The calibrated CNs are situated between the optimal CN for high and the optimal CN for low events. For standard and complacent behaviour high events will be overestimated and low events will be underestimated. On a long-term scale, these under- and overestimations are likely to balance out. However, this assumption depends on the relative occurrence of large events compared to small events. For example, if many large events occur within a short period of time, the long-time *surface runoff* is likely to be underestimated.

There are only few studies assessing the accuracy of the *surface runoff* in SWAT applications. Presumably, this due to the difficulty of the practical application of *surface runoff* measurements. However, several studies validating daily surface runoff, the anticipated trend – underestimation of low and overestimation of high surface runoff – could be observed (Mishra et al., 2007) (Tripathi et al., 2003) (Behera et al, 2006). For a robust assessment of this effect, an extensive assessment of the *surface runoff* on many different datasets would be needed.

(xxxii) Mean absolute Error as Goodness of Fit Measure

In the Switzerland case study region, to measure the deviation of the estimates from the observed *direct runoffs* the MAE was used as goodness of fit measure. The MAE was chosen to provide a simple estimate of the expected accuracy of the SCS-CN method and to allow an assessment of the different forms of the SCS-Cn method (i.e. calibrated, composited, distributed).

However, looking at the MAE results it can be observed that the variability in the precipitation-*direct runoff* relationship increases with higher precipitation intensity. Aggregating the MAE over a large range of events is therefore likely to overestimate the MAE of the events at the smaller end of the range and underestimate the MAE of the events at higher end of the range. In a further analysis it could be differentiated between several sub-ranges to mitigate this problem. The same problem appears when considering the CN as a random variable and fitting a distribution function to the observed *P-Q*-pairs over a wide range of precipitation inputs. As the variability often increases with increasing precipitation the corresponding distribution function is likely to be wider for larger precipitation inputs. Hereby the growing inaccuracies of measured data might be important.

(xxxiii) CNs from experimental Plots

As already indicated in section (iv) the tabulated CNs estimates in the NEH-4 were not determined by homogeneous watersheds but were empirically determined from watersheds with often multiple LULCs and soil types. Some authors that assume the SCS-CN method to calculate *surface runoff* have thus investigated the watershed response of homogeneous plots. One large study was performed was performed Lal et al. in 2016. Here, the precipitation-*surface runoff* relationship was investigated experimentally for 27 agricultural plots in India. The authors concluded that generally the CN estimates

form the NEH-4 were poor as “P–Q derived CNs are higher than those from NEH-4 tables. However, these are closer for higher CN values, which is consistent with the general notion that the existing SCS-CN method performs better for high P–Q (or CN) events.” (Lal et al., 2016, p.164)

This result is in line with the notion of the secondary P effect and the statement in the NEH-4 that the CN estimates are made for large precipitation events in the near-constant CN range. This also means that one has to be especially careful when using tabulated values for modelling the *runoff* for low precipitation events.

(xxxiii) Data Quality

The data quality is essential for the validation of the model. If the measured precipitation-*direct runoff* pairs are far off the real values, the validity assessment is likely to ascribe a worse performance than there actually is. Furthermore, in the high precipitation and streamflow range, for which the SCS-CN method has originally been constructed, the measurements generally have a higher uncertainty than in the low range. Cleaning of the datasets is likely to improve the MAE.

(xxxiv) The Importance of Baseflow Contribution Estimation

The Institute of Hydrology (1980) approach is a simple algorithm for determining the baseflow contribution of a given streamflow. As the *direct runoff* is very much dependent on the baseflow, the way, the baseflow contribution is determined is essential. This counts especially for the low precipitation events as in these cases the *direct runoff* is generally small and an erroneous baseflow contribution can have a stronger relative influence. This has also been shown in section 4 for one extreme outlier in the intermediately forested watershed in Columbia.

(xxxv) Daily Measurements of Precipitation-Direct Runoff Pairs

In all three case studies daily precipitation and *direct runoff* measurements were used. As already described in section 4, the use of daily values instead of individual events might lead to wrong allocation of direct runoff, for example if the causative precipitation fell the day before. This is particularly problematic if the lag between precipitation input and direct runoff is large, i.e. a part tail of the event hydrograph is allocated on the next day. Large lags often occur for large, flat, and elongated watersheds.

In an interview Victor Mockus (1996), the originator of the SCS-CN stated, that the method was “developed for events” based on daily data, “because that was the only data available in large quantities”. The errors introduced by wrong allocation are actually also included as source of variability which is accounted for when defining a CN as a random variable. (Hawkins, 1978) (Hjelmfelt et al., 1981)

Clearing the datasets for erroneous allocation of direct runoff is likely to improve the MAE of the model. The SCS-CN method is likely to perform better on the event scale as the validity assessment is suggesting.

(xxxvi) Reconsidering the secondary P effect

Considering the discussion presented in section (xxxiii), (xxxiv), and (xxxv) it gets clear that the uncertainties from data quality, baseflow contribution estimation, and erroneous allocation of direct runoff to its causative precipitation event have a significant influence on the validity assessment. This raises the question if the secondary P effect might not be solely caused by these uncertainties.

In this context it is interesting to consider the analysis conducted in the Kenya case study region. In the Mukogodo and Ituuri watershed no baseflow was occurring which eliminates the error caused by erroneous baseflow contribution calculations. Furthermore, only days were considered that had only 5mm of precipitation on the previous and the following day. Also, the *direct runoff* was always determined for two consecutive days. This procedure prevents erroneous allocation of *direct runoffs*.

Still, in the Kenya case study region in all watersheds a secondary P effect could be observed. This is indicating that the secondary is not only caused by uncertainties in the low precipitation but also a typical way of watershed response behaviour. Further analysis could help to shed light on this issue.

8. Recommendations

For future applications of the WOCAT SLM Watershed Tool the following recommendations can be provided based on the findings of this thesis:

- The WT is a good tool for estimating and presenting the influence of land cover, land use, and sustainable land management practices on floods. The numerous different ways of presenting the output of the model in the QGIS interface is a strength of the WT.
- The WT should only be used for large events. The *secondary P effect* often leads to an underestimation of small *runoffs* (for standard and complacent behaviour). Also, because of this, the application of the water balance approach is not recommended.
- The concept of AMC should only be considered as surrogate for the total variability (i.e. as a proxy for 10% and 90% exceedance of event-wise optimized CNs). It should not be used based on 5-days antecedent precipitation.
- Using the table values provided for the CNs causes the WT to be unreliable – therefore in these circumstances the WT should not be used for planning purposes.

9. Practical Issues of Watershed Tool

In the following some challenges and suggested improvements concerning the practical implementation of the SCS-CN method in the WT and the visual outputs are presented. The problem statements are taken from a collection of problems concerning the WT (ToDo) (see Digital Appendix, To Dos for WOCAT SLM Watershed Tool) and from the Changelog from October 2020 (Log) (see Digital Appendix, Wocat Watershed Tool Change Log Oct 2020). For some improvements, the working style file had to be adapted. The modified version of the working style file can be found in the Digital Appendix und the name `working_style_3.14_Joschua.qml`.

1. Problem Statement (ToDo, 3.):

When inserting the parameters for the CN calculation in the Feature Attributes window.

The window has to be closed and reopened several times. It would be more user-friendly if each time the window is closed, the python script is run 3times. Even if this means that the process will take 2-3 seconds, this will help a lot.

Commentary:

This is the most time-consuming problem of the WT, as it concerns the way, the WT is built, i.e. how the *QGIS Python Init Code Configuration* is designed. There are two options for changing inputs for a given watershed HRU. It can either be done via the *feature form* or the *attribute table*. If an input is changed in the *feature form*, the window has to be reopened twice. However, if an input is changed with the *attribute table* only one reopening is needed. The *formOpen* function is run every time when either the *feature form* or the *attribute table* is opened. This is the reason why it takes more than one reopening of the window. Calculations based on the change input are only computed when the window is opened. The difference between the *feature form* and the *attribute table* is that when the *attribute table* is closed, the adaptations are already saved. In the *feature form*, this is not the case. The *feature form* uses and adapts the values in the *attribute table*. When the *feature form* is reopened the first time, the *formOpen* function is run and the previously entered inputs are added to the *attribute table*. However, the calculations are still computed based on the values of the previous step. The correct values do not appear in the *feature form* until the window is reopened a second time.

This problem cannot be solved within the given computational structure.

2. Problem Statement (Log, d.):

The curve number corrected for Slope is calculated but it seems that the value "Slope" doesn't really influence the calculation, therefore it's likely that the calculation formula that was implemented by sourcepole seems to be wrong. Calculation needs to be reviewed by Hanspeter:

cn_2 is the variable that comes from either the curve number value map or from the adjusted curve number. Following calculation is done further:

$$cn_3 = cn_2 * \exp(0.00673 * (100 - cn_2))$$

$$cn_slope = (1. / 3) * (cn_3 - cn_2) * (1 - 2 * \exp(-13.86 * slope)) + cn_2$$

If cn_slope doesn't change upon changing the slope value, the slope factor seems to be irrelevant in the above calculation.

Commentary:

The WT applies a slope accounting following Sharpley & Williams (1990) which use slope with a unit of m/m. However, the WT asks for %.

In all previous applications of the WT the slope has been inserted in % which is a factor 100 larger than the slope in m/m demanded by Sharpley & Williams method. With high slopes the term $(1 - 2e^{-13.86\alpha})$ in equation (19) approaches 1. Thus, in previous studies practically all CNs were increased by a value of approximately $\frac{1}{3}(CN_{III} - CN_{II})$ which often produces a significant overestimation.

Solution:

To eliminate this error, the formOpen file has been adapted. The calculation has been changed such that the slope can still be implemented as % but the WT converts it to m/m.

3. Problem Statement (ToDo, 6.):

The Layer Styling for "input Rainfall" and "Watershed Contribution" are not working.

Commentary:

This error occurred because the related equations were not implemented correctly.

Solution:

This bug was fixed by adapting the equations in the category Symbology and saved to the working style file.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Watershed Contribution	(no filter)
<input type="checkbox"/>	0% - 1% Watershed Contribution	"UnitRoAre" < 1
<input type="checkbox"/>	1% - 5% Watershed Contribution	"UnitRoAre" >= 1 AND "UnitRoAre" < 5
<input type="checkbox"/>	5% - 10% Watershed Contribution	"UnitRoAre" >= 5 AND "UnitRoAre" < 10
<input type="checkbox"/>	10% - 20% Watershed Contribution	"UnitRoAre" >= 10 AND "UnitRoAre" < 20
<input type="checkbox"/>	20% - 50% Watershed Contribution	"UnitRoAre" >= 20 AND "UnitRoAre" < 50
<input type="checkbox"/>	50%+ Watershed Contribution	"UnitRoAre" >= 50
<input type="checkbox"/>	Input Rainfall	(no filter)
<input type="checkbox"/>	0-10mm Input Rainfall	"AvgRainfal" >= 0 AND "AvgRainfal" < 10
<input type="checkbox"/>	10-20mm Input Rainfall	"AvgRainfal" >= 10 AND "AvgRainfal" < 20
<input type="checkbox"/>	20-50mm Input Rainfall	"AvgRainfal" >= 20 AND "AvgRainfal" < 50
<input type="checkbox"/>	50-80mm Input Rainfall	"AvgRainfal" >= 50 AND "AvgRainfal" < 80
<input type="checkbox"/>	80-110mm Input Rainfall	"AvgRainfal" >= 80 AND "AvgRainfal" < 110
<input type="checkbox"/>	110mm+ Input Rainfall	"AvgRainfal" >= 110

Figure 44. Adapted formulation for the Symbology of the Watershed Contribution and Input Precipitation layer styling.

10. Appendix

Surface Runoff Component of the Soil & Water Assessment Tool

The SWAT model is a physically-based and semi-distributed watershed model (small watershed to basin scale) which is often used for assessing the impact of land use, land management practices and climate change on quantity and quality of surface and ground water. It allows the modelling the flow of nutrients, pesticides, and sediments. Also, it is often applied to ungauged watersheds. The revised version of SWAT, SWAT+ was introduced in 2016 (Bieger et al., 2016). SWAT+ further includes an enhanced extensive plant growth component allowing for very detailed input of LULC over the course of the year. Within SWAT there is a differentiation between landscape processes and channel processes. The landscape is organized in the following way: a given basin/watershed is subdivided into different sub-basins/watersheds which are again divided into *hydrological response units* (HRUs). Furthermore, in the improved version (SWAT+) so called *landscape units* (LSU) are added in between (Tech, 2021). On the HRU stage, the water flows are modelled between the soil surface and soil reservoirs which are divided into three categories – root zone, unsaturated zone, and saturated zone. SWAT is usually applied for daily time-steps, but finer temporal resolutions are possible. The SCS-CN method is used to determine the Q with equation (4). It is also possible to model the *runoff* using the Green-Ampt equation, this option is however less popular in applications. In SWAT, Q is called *runoff*, *surface runoff* or *precipitation excess* and is used analogously to the term previously defined as *overland flow* (unchanneled water flowing over the surface). Water can reach a channel as *surface runoff* or as lateral flow from one of the soil reservoirs. Water is allocated as input to the adjacent channel by accounting for lag if the time of concentration is larger than one day. The lag is calculated differently for the different reservoirs. In the channel, flow rate and velocity are calculated using Manning's equation and water is routed in using variable storage routing or Muskingum routing, both variations of the kinematic wave approach. (Nietsch et al., 2009)

CNs are determined for each HRU individually. Generally, the CN_{II} is constant over a longer simulation period, i.e. one month. However, the user has the option to vary the CN_{II} based on plant, tillage or kill operation. There are two options how the long-term CN is further varied on a daily scale – either by creating a dependence on soil profile water content or evapotranspiration. In the case S is varied with soil profile water content, the following equation is used:

$$S = S_{max} \left(1 - \frac{SW}{(SW + e^{w_1 - w_2 \cdot SW})} \right) \quad (38)$$

where S_{max} [mm] is the maximum value of the retention parameter S for a given day, SW [mm] is the soil profile water content excluding the amount of water held at the wilting point, w_1 and w_2 are shape coefficients. S_{max} is calculated by equation (5) using CN_I from equation (17) and CN_{III} from equation (18). w_1 and w_2 are calculated with the following equations:

$$w_1 = \ln \left(\frac{FC}{1 - S_3 \cdot S_{max}^{-1}} - FC \right) + w_2 \cdot FC \quad (39)$$

$$w_2 = \frac{\left(\ln \left(\frac{FC}{1 - S_3 \cdot S_{max}^{-1}} - FC \right) - \ln \left(\frac{SAT}{1 - 2.54 \cdot S_{max}^{-1}} - SAT \right) \right)}{(SAT - FC)} \quad (40)$$

where FC [mm] is the amount of water in the soil profile at field capacity, S_3 [mm] is the retention parameter for CN_{III} , SAT [mm] is the amount of water in the soil profile, when completely saturated.

from equations (38), (39), and (40) follows that:

- S for CN_i corresponds to the amount of soil water at wilting point
- S for CN_{III} corresponds to the amount of soil water at field capacity
- $S = 254$ and hence $CN = 99$ when the soil is completely saturated

Hereby, CN_i and CN_{III} are calculated using equations (17) and (18). In its approach SWAT is directly connecting the AMC accounting form the SCS-CN method with soil moisture. (Nietsch et al., 2009)

In the case S is varied with evapotranspiration, the following equation is used:

$$S = S_{prev} + E_o e^{\frac{-cncoef \cdot S_{prev}}{S_{max}}} - P + Q \quad (41)$$

where S_{prev} [mm] is the retention parameter of the previous day, E_o [mm d⁻¹] is the potential evapotranspiration, and $cncoef$ is the weighting coefficient.

This option was added as an alternative to the soil moisture method that overestimated the *surface runoff* for shallow soils. It makes the CN more dependent on antecedent climate. (Nietsch et al., 2009)

Figure 45. Relative sensitivity of Q to CN for CNs between 30 and 100, P between 0 and 140mm for a λ of 0.2.

$$S_{i,j}^{CN} = \frac{CN_{i,j}}{Q_{i,j}} \frac{Q_{i-1,j} + Q_{i+1,j}}{CN_{i-1,j} + CN_{i+1,j}} \quad (42)$$

where i is the index of the CN , j is the index of the P , $S_{i,j}^{CN}$ is the relative sensitivity of $Q_{i,j}$ to the CN .

$$S = \frac{P}{\lambda} + \frac{(1 - \lambda)Q - \sqrt{(1 - \lambda)^2 Q^2 + 4\lambda P Q}}{2\lambda^2} \quad (43)$$

$$M = 0.5 \left(-(1 + \lambda)S + \sqrt{(1 - \lambda^2 S^2 + 4P_5 S)} \right) \quad (44)$$

Table 11. With the Watershed Tool estimated precipitation-direct runoff relationships for the intermediately forested and deforested Columbian watershed for AMC_i , AMC_{II} , AMC_{III} .

Watershed	Estimated Direct Runoff [mm]					
	Intermediately Forested			Deforested		
Precipitation Input [mm]	CN_i	CN_{II}	CN_{III}	CN_i	CN_{II}	CN_{III}
5	-	-	0.1	-	-	0.1
10	-	-	0.7	-	0.0	1.0
20	-	0.0	4.2	-	0.5	5.5
30	0.0	0.4	9.9	0.0	2.2	11.9
40	0.2	1.4	16.7	0.2	5.1	19.4
50	0.6	3.6	24.3	0.9	9.2	27.6
60	1.3	6.9	32.5	2.0	14.1	36.1
70	2.4	11.1	41.0	3.7	19.6	45.0

80	4.1	16.0	49.7	6.0	25.7	54.1
90	6.3	21.4	58.7	8.8	32.3	63.3

Table 12. Percentile of the CN_I and CN_{III} determined for the calibrated CN_{II} for all the investigated Swiss watersheds considering the optimized CN for all events above 50mm.

ID	Percentile CN_I	Percentile CN_{III}
2251	20	85
2300	14	91
2305	16	85
2343	0	100
2374	10	93
2436	25	85
2486	14	99
2604	3	94
2608	13	89
2609	5	90
2610	15	94
Average	12	91

Table 13. Land use categories along MacMillan and adapted land use categories and hydrologic conditions for the application of the WT for the Kenya case study region.

Category along MacMillan (n.d.)	CN_{II}			
	A	B	C	D
good Grass	39	61	74	80
sparse Grass	49	69	79	84
bare Grass	68	79	86	89
2-20% treed good Grass	38	60	74	80
2-20% treed sparse Grass	47	68	78	83
2-20% treed bare Grass	64	77	84	88
20-50% treed good Grass	35	59	73	79
20-50% treed sparse Grass	42	65	76	82
20-50% treed (ericaceous) good Grass	35	59	73	79
20-50% treed (ericaceous) sparse Grass	42	65	76	82
>50% dense treed (ericaceous) good Grass	24	51	62	70
Crop	58	72	81	85
2-20% treed Crop	55	70	80	84
>50% dense Trees	18	47	57	65
Road	74	84	90	92

Table 14. Possible combinations of land use type, structural measure, hydrologic condition, and hydrologic soil type. (from Lininger et al., 2020)

Land use type	Structural Measure	Version 1 - USDA Only				
		Hydrologic condition	A	B	C	D
Runoff curve numbers for Cropland						
Ca: Annual cropping	not specified	Poor	66	76	82	85
		Good	62	73	80	84

	Straight Row	Poor	69	79	86	90
		Good	65	77	84	88
	Straight Row and Crop Residue Cover	Poor	68	78	85	88
		Good	62	74	81	85
	Contoured	Poor	67	77	83	87
		Good	63	74	82	85
	Contoured and Crop Residue Cover	Poor	66	76	82	86
		Good	62	73	81	84
	Contoured and Terraced	Poor	64	73	80	82
		Good	61	71	78	81
	Contoured and Terraced and Crop Residue cover	Poor	63	72	79	81
		Good	60	70	77	80
Cp: Perennial (non-woody) cropping	not specified	Poor	64	75	83	86
		Good	55	69	78	83
	Straight Row	Poor	66	77	85	89
		Good	58	72	81	85
	Contoured	Poor	64	75	83	85
		Good	55	69	78	83
	Contoured and Terraced	Poor	63	73	80	83
		Good	51	67	76	80
Ct: Tree and shrub cropping		Poor	64	75	83	86
		Good	55	69	78	83

Runoff curve numbers for Grazingland		Hydrologic condition	A	B	C	D
Ge: Extensive grazing land	Poor		68	80	87	91
	Fair		49	70	80	87
	Good		39	62	74	83
Gi: Intensive grazing/ fodder production	---		30	58	71	78
Runoff curve numbers for Forests / woodlands		Hydrologic condition	A	B	C	D
Fn: Natural	Poor		54	70	80	85
	Fair		46	58	69	76
	Good		40	46	60	67

Fp: Plantations, afforestations	Poor	45	66	77	83
	Fair	36	60	73	79
	Good	30	55	70	77
Fo: Other	Poor	57	73	82	86
	Fair	43	65	76	82
	Good	32	58	72	79

Runoff curve numbers for Mixed	Hydrologic condition	A	B	C	D
Mf: Agroforestry	Poor	57	73	82	86
	Fair	43	65	76	82
	Good	32	58	72	79
Mp: Agro-pastoralism	Poor	57	73	82	86
	Fair	43	65	76	82
	Good	32	58	72	79
Ma: Agro-silvopastoralism	Poor	57	73	82	86
	Fair	43	65	76	82
	Good	32	58	72	79
Ms: Silvo-pastoralism	Poor	57	73	82	86
	Fair	43	65	76	82
	Good	32	58	72	79
Mo: Other	Poor	57	73	82	86
	Fair	43	65	76	82
	Good	32	58	72	79

Runoff curve numbers for Other	Hydrologic condition	A	B	C	D
Oi: Mines and extractive industries	none	X	X	X	X
Os: Settlements, infrastructure networks	none	43	65	76	82
Ow: Waterways, drainage lines, ponds, dams	none	X	X	X	X
Oo: Other	none	76	85	90	92

Table 15. Watershed ID along Bundesamt für Umwelt, Abteilung Hydrologie (2020), and fitted 2nd order polynomial from the estimated precipitation-direct runoff pairs for the months June-September and April, May, and October using the distributed CN approach for several watersheds in Switzerland

Watershed ID	Fitted 2 nd order polynomial		
	CN _I	CN _{II}	CN _{III}
2251	J-S: 0.0022P ² + 0.0466P - 2.3658 A-M,O: 0.0022P ² + 0.1838P - 6.3569	J-S: 0.0016P ² + 0.4518P - 12.914 A-M,O: 0.0013P ² + 0.57P - 13.98	J-S: 0.0007P ² + 0.7846P - 14.812 A-M,O: 0.0005P ² + 0.8399P - 13.456
2300	J-S: 0.0022P ² + 0.0139P - 2.9067 A-M,O: 0.0021P ² + 0.1374P - 6.362	J-S: 0.0016P ² + 0.4356P - 13.621 A-M,O: 0.0013P ² + 0.539P - 14.434	J-S: 0.0007P ² + 0.778P - 15.379 A-M,O: 0.0006P ² + 0.8254P - 14.122
2305	J-S: 0.0023P ² + 0.0388P - 5.4015 A-M,O: 0.0022P ² + 0.1446P - 8.3724	J-S: 0.0015P ² + 0.4833P - 15.302 A-M,O: 0.0013P ² + 0.5722P - 16.016	J-S: 0.0006P ² + 0.8104P - 15.302 A-M,O: 0.0005P ² + 0.8515P - 14.55
2343	J-S: 0.0021P ² + 0.0671P - 2.388 A-M,O: 0.0022P ² + 0.1463P - 4.6227	J-S: 0.0015P ² + 0.4581P - 12.511 A-M,O: 0.0014P ² + 0.5249P - 13.059	J-S: 0.0007P ² + 0.7829P - 14.429 A-M,O: 0.0006P ² + 0.814P - 13.635
2374	J-S: 0.0023P ² + 0.0193P - 4.2011 A-M,O: 0.0021P ² + 0.1534P - 7.8752	J-S: 0.0016P ² + 0.4546P - 14.545 A-M,O: 0.0013P ² + 0.5651P - 15.351	J-S: 0.0007P ² + 0.7916P - 15.599 A-M,O: 0.0005P ² + 0.842P - 14.219
2436	J-S: 0.0023P ² - 0.0364P - 0.7882 A-M,O: 0.0021P ² + 0.0589P - 3.4049	J-S: 0.0017P ² + 0.3739P - 12.428 A-M,O: 0.0015P ² + 0.4525P - 13.005	J-S: 0.0008P ² + 0.7389P - 15.556 A-M,O: 0.0007P ² + 0.7747P - 14.576
2486	J-S: 0.0023P ² - 0.0138P - 2.6531 A-M,O: 0.0022P ² + 0.0863P - 5.4261	J-S: 0.0017P ² + 0.4134P - 13.68 A-M,O: 0.0014P ² + 0.4965P - 14.312	J-S: 0.0007P ² + 0.7658P - 15.697 A-M,O: 0.0006P ² + 0.8039P - 14.674
2604	J-S: 0.0022P ² - 0.0157P - 0.9251 A-M,O: 0.0021P ² + 0.0665P - 3.1862	J-S: 0.0017P ² + 0.3854P - 12.223 A-M,O: 0.0015P ² + 0.4534P - 12.729	J-S: 0.0008P ² + 0.7427P - 15.253 A-M,O: 0.0007P ² + 0.7738P - 14.412
2608	J-S: 0.0021P ² + 0.0711P - 1.72 A-M,O: 0.0022P ² + 0.1476P - 4.0422	J-S: 0.0015P ² + 0.4496P - 11.896 A-M,O: 0.0014P ² + 0.5181P - 12.608	J-S: 0.0007P ² + 0.7759P - 14.223 A-M,O: 0.0006P ² + 0.8095P - 13.513
2609	J-S: 0.0023P ² - 0.0279P - 1.89 A-M,O: 0.0022P ² + 0.0673P - 4.5085	J-S: 0.0017P ² + 0.3909P - 13.13 A-M,O: 0.0015P ² + 0.4695P - 13.711	J-S: 0.0008P ² + 0.7496P - 15.664 A-M,O: 0.0007P ² + 0.7855P - 14.686
2610	J-S: 0.0023P ² - 0.01P - 1.8549 A-M,O: 0.0021P ² + 0.0863P - 4.5182	J-S: 0.0017P ² + 0.4041P - 12.972 A-M,O: 0.0015P ² + 0.4839P - 13.575	J-S: 0.0008P ² + 0.757P - 15.429 A-M,O: 0.0007P ² + 0.7935P - 14.442

Table 16. The different land use categories of the Arealstatistik NOLU04 and (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2017) and the corresponding land use categories, and hydrologic conditions from the documentation of the watershed tool (Liniger et al., 2020).

Category NOLU04	Watershed Tool Category	Hydrologic Condition
-----------------	-------------------------	----------------------

Industrie- und Gewerbeareal > 1 ha	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Industrie- und Gewerbeareal < 1 ha	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Ein- und Zweifamilienhausareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Reihen- und Terrassenhausareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Mehrfamilienhausareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Öffentliches Gebäudeareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Landwirtschaftliches Gebäudeareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Nicht spezifiziertes Gebäudeareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Autobahnareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Strassenareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Parkplatzareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Bahnareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Flugplatzareal	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Energieversorgungsanlagen	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Abwasserreinigungsanlagen	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Übrige Ver- und Entsorgungsanlagen	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Deponien	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Abbau	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Baustellen	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Bau- und Siedlungsbrachen	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Öffentliche Parkanlagen	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Sportanlagen	Os: Settlements, Infrastructure, networks	-
Golfplätze	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good April, May, October: fine
Campingplätze	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good April, May, October: fine
Schrebergärten	Ca: Annual cropping – not specified	June-September: good April, May, October: poor
Friedhöfe	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good April, May, October: fine
Obstbau	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good

		April, May, October: fine
Rebbau	Mf: Agroforestry	poor
Gartenbau	Ca: Annual cropping – not specified	June-September: good April, May, October: poor
Ackerland i.w.S.	Ca: Annual cropping – not specified	June-September: good April, May, October: poor
Naturwiesen i.w.S.	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good April, May, October: fine
Heimweiden i.w.S.	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good April, May, October: fine
Alpwiesen i.w.S.	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good April, May, October: fine
Alp- und Juraweiden i.w.S.	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good April, May, October: fine
Schafalpen i.w.S.	Ge: Extensive grazing land	June-September: good April, May, October: fine
Waldbestände	Fn: Natural	good
Aufforstungen	Fn: Natural	good
Holzschläge	Fn: Natural	good
Waldschäden	Fn: Natural	good
Seen	Water	-
Flüsse, Bäche	Water	-
Hochwasserverbauungen	Water	-
Keine Nutzung	Other	-
Lawinen- und Steinschlagverbauungen	Other	-
Alpine Sportinfrastruktur	Other	-
Landschaftseingriffe	Other	-

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